

On the victimology of Ukraine-Russia conflict 2014-(2024)

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Abstract

Only in Europa during 20th Century there have been accounted for 22955000 (+) victims of crime of genocide. By targeting of potential groups of people-victims of genocide, there are described their cultures, their religions, their histories, linguistic characteristics, archeological data, ethnic/genetic components *et cetera*; thus, adopting historical, psychological, sociological, and cultural approaches, among others. Despite the fact that, the victim-group (people) of genocide is seldom a State, the Ukraine-Russia conflict starts with Ukrainian armed attack of ethnic Russians (minority) in Ukraine (Donbass) in 2014 — in Donbass (1989) there are 3595000 ethnic Russians or 44 % of the total population; in total, there is 22 % ethnic Russians in Ukraine since 21.12.1991 (Alma Ata Treaty) — and the currently stage of the continuous conflict shows increasing in number and gravity of crimes against Russian-ethnics, including in their territory and involving mass murder of civilian Russians of territory of Russia; attacking civilian towns and villages, urban infrastructure, burning down civilian houses and other buildings, including cultural monuments, *et cetera*, in addition to mass murders forced Ukrainization, racialization, religious banning, and more, of Ukrainian territory over the recent decade. Most recently escalation of the conflict shows Ukrainian force armed attack of the territory of independent and sovereign State Russia on 06.08.2024 (5.30h.) Non governmental organizations monitor violent genocidal cases and situations; document genocides; if any, and offer opinions on (pre)genocidal cases. The research on crime of genocide has expanded not only legally, but also to social science and humanities. Despite, enormous effort made, so far, there is a lack of knowledge how to prevent cases of crime of genocide as well as whether genocide can be deterred; furthermore, accounting for the fact that preventing or ending crime of genocide through international intervention is very difficult task. The criminology practice, so far has show some common characteristics of cases of genocide. They have been systematized into case-questionnaires*; thus, addressing a set of questions looking at seven stages of the crime. A monitoring of crimes of Ukrainian military forces against ethnic Russians as minority in Ukraine and as majority people in Russia within the period 2014-2024 potentially shapes Ukrainian State's intent of committing crime of genocide against ethnic Russians; thus, determining ethnic Russians as potential victim-group (people) and Russia as a potential victim-State. This contribution attempts early sketch on the issue *via* criminological lens in respect to stages of genocide and key-questions, which should be addressed in recognizing the Ukrainian military staff/forces crimes, so far as crime of genocide. The author adopts a strong personal view and offers a new way of connecting numerous crimes committed by Ukrainian armed forces against ethnic Russians and against their independent and sovereign State Russia, not only because of Article 53(2)(c) states that Prosecutor concludes is there or not a sufficient basis for a prosecution as well as the Prosecutor is able to initiate investigations *proprio motu* under Article 15 of the Rome Statute, but also because of there is current trend in political though that the committed by Ukrainian military forces crimes against ethnic Russians including destroying their State (Russia) to be *a priori* classified as acts of “self-defense”. The author's hope, in the latter context, is that this contribution shall argue the reader for obvious concerns how we should reflect and normative prescript not only the Ukrainian armed attack of the territory of Russia on 06.08.2024, but also the committed, so far crimes against ethnic Russians in both the territories of Ukraine and Russia by armed forces of State Ukraine.

*N. Rafter, The Crime of All Crimes, Toward a Criminology of Genocide, New York University Press, New York (2016) [ISBN: 9781479814916]; (Appendix B, pp. 235-238.)

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Bulgaria: NATO Member State
(Region: Balkan, South-East Europe)

There is used a template of map of present-day administrative areas of States.
The shown boundaries of the Ancient States are only approximated.
The adapted maps are cited accordingly.
The flags, respectively, names of both the old and present-day States are shown.

838-972 Rus' Empire

882: Rus' King Oleg only occupied Atelkuzu (present-day Kiev region) and Hungarians levied taxes on the Rus' Empire.

Socio-political system:
Military-Democracy

Atelkuzu (or Etekköz)

Hungarian confederation

It was intervened into
Byzantine-Bulgarian war

05.04.971: Rus' King† Svyatoslav captured the old capital of Bulgarian Empire (Preslav' — Capital of Bulgarian Empire 839-972) and captured the Bulgarian King Boris II.

Hungary: NATO Member State
(Region: Central-Europe)

Bulgarian Empire

†In the chronicle of West Roman emperors of the Saxon dynasty Bishop Thietmar of Merseburg (975-1018) refers to Vladimir (or to his son Yaroslav the Wise) as 'Ruscorum-Ruscuorum-Ruscenorum rex', i.e. 'King of the Ruthenians'. The coronation of Vladimir is as King-Emperor of Rus'.

Great
Poland

972-1188
Rus' Empire

930 (944?): King Igor captured
garrison Kiev

1037: Created city Kiev

Kiev (Kiroffo)
(garrison)

Galicja principality: It was found
12th CE by King Vladimir (son of
King Jaroslav the Wise).

Poland: NATO Member State
(Region: Central Europe)

Dobrudzha

Great Poland

V(W)olyn

1190

Rus' Empire

Hungarian Kingdom

Galicia (part): The province had neither history nor territory of its own or it is only geography area (p. 156).
1188/9 it is integrated into Hungarian Kingdom as *Rex Galiciae* since King Bela III.

1290-1470 Rus' Empire

1471 Province (oblast) Kiev was liquidated.

Galicia (part):
1387 it is integrated into the Poland Kingdom.

The Empire of the Golden Horde
(Mongolia)

1590-1654 Russian Empire

1617: Radical counter-Reformation of the Church and forcible joining of the Orthodox population with the Uniate Church; particularly, highlighting people from Polotsk, Vitebsk, Mogilëv, Mstislavl, and more. The cities were targeted in the Uniate dioceses and the Orthodox Church buildings were deprived by force^[1].

Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth

Eastern-Slavic lands with Polish Government. The Commonwealth nobles enjoyed exclusive powers on their own lands.

1596: Eastern Orthodox Christianity doctrine fold. Orthodox Church in the Commonwealth split into two: Uniate and Orthodox (Disuniate)^[1]. There was/is divided religious allegiances between Eastern Orthodoxy and Western Greek Catholic church (Uniate church), combining Eastern (Christianity) Orthodox rite with Roman Catholic (Christianity) doctrine.

1596 Union of Brest: The territory belongs to Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth from former Rus' principalities^[1]. Roman Catholic Church was aggressively encroaching upon Rus' lands^[1].

1654: Bohdan Khmelnickij and Ukrainian ethnics (*zemskij sobor*) were challenged the Polish rule appealing against the Polish rules to the Government in Moscow.

Lithuania: NATO Member State
(Region: North Europe)

[1] Y. Aoshima, Entangled interactions between religions and national consciousness in Central and Eastern Europe, Academic Studies Press, Boston, 2020, ISBN: 9781644693568.

1648-1750 Russian Empire

1705: Peter the Great entered Polotsk^[1].

1686: The Russian Empire were taken the control over Kiev against the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth.

1648: The so-called „The Hetmanate“^{*} territory is at about 56.6% of the province „Little Russia“ (below.)

Despite, it has been equalized territorially with „Little Russia“ (Malorossiiia) (p. 17^{*}). Therefore, there is discrepancy, regarding the factual territory called „The Hatmanate“ (compare data on p. 17^{*} and p. 142^{**}.) Consider the map of province Little Russia (below) and ist polygon area value.

The term Hetmanate has been wrongly applied to present-day Ukraine, as well (p.7^{*}.) As the polygon area data, below, the territory of the Hetmanate is only at about 0.02 % of the territory of Ukraine in 1945.

1692-1702: The the Orthodox Church in mainly present-day West Ukraine cities became Uniatic officially^[1]. The Uniatic Church policy during that time had anti-Orthodox character; excluded Orthodox people and marginalized them^[1].

Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth

Kiev

Poltava

1648: The Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth had attempted to establish control over the military bands via their recognition. The available registers fluctuate. Despite, there were 1300 (1568), 6000 (1625), and 8000 (1630.) Data also show 41200 people (1621.) The Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth had registered 6000 people (1625.)

1665: Petro Doroshenko had formed Dnieper Cossack^{***} (military bands)-Ottoman Empire Tatars^{***} alliance turning the territory into „The Ruin“ (a historiography term used to that time) (p.27^{*}.)

1648: The so-called „The Hetmanate“^{*} originated. There were Poles, Catholics, Uniates, and Jews (p.24^{*}.) It has been highlighted as no man’s land between the Ottoiman Empire and the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth (p.24^{*};) thus, lacking a state’s administration. The non-settled people were organized into military bands.

^{**}Regarding applications of term *Tatar* from Crimea in 16th CE and present-day research texts can be seen below together with data on term *Tat* used to group people and their ethnicity in Crimea during that time as well as in the Ottoman Empire registers from 1529 and 1545.

^{***} The *Dnieper Cossack* from 18th CE should be distinguished from *Dan Cossack*, because of genetic data on the latter group people show that they were East Slavs (Russians)^[1], while the former group people were associated with Circassian or Adyge speaking *Qipçaq*s (*Kipçak*) dialect and *Shapsugs* (North Ossetians) (see below ethno-linguistic relation among some ethnics from the conflict territory - object of the current study.

^{*} The map is adapted to: Z. Kohut, *Russian Centralism and Ukrainian Autonomy*, 1988, Harvard Ukrainian Research Institute Press, ISBN 0916458172 (p. xiv)

^{**} The map is adapted to: J. le Donne, *The Territorial Reform of the Russian Empire 1775-1796. II: The Borderlands, 1777-1796*. Cahiers du Monde russe et soviétique, 24 (1983) 411-457 (p. 421).

[1] Y. Aoshima, *Entangled interactions between religions and national consciousness in Central and Eastern Europe*, Academic Studies Press, Boston, 2020 [ISBN: 9781644693568].

1770-1772 Russian Empire

Austro-Hungarian Empire

Türkei: NATO Member State (Region: Near-East)

Volyn: 1772 is integrated into Austro-Hungarian Empire and Habsburgian officials (p. 156).

1772: 82597 (51.66%) Poles; 29325 (18.34%) Ukrainians; in total 159887 people (p.151^[1].) Jews were the third ethnic group.

Galicia (part): 1772 is integrated into Austro-Hungarian Empire and Habsburgian officials (p. 156).

Empty and lacking development land belonging formally to Russian Empire during that time.

Empty and lacking development land belonging formally to Ottoman Empire during that time.

Principality of Moldova

No-man's land

No-man's land

Lviv (Lemberg/Lwow)

[1] Y. Aoshima, Entangled interactions between religions and national consciousness in Central and Eastern Europe, Academic Studies Press, Boston, 2020, ISBN: 9781644693568.

1815-1875 Russian Empire

03.05.(09.06) 1815: Congress of Vienna.
There was created Congress Kingdom of Poland ruled by the Russian Empire within 1815-1874.

1867: Galician autonomy.
There was strength dominance of Poles in education, economy, and self-government. It became the only political territory led by Poles in the Austro-Hungarian Empire.

The Russian Empire and Austria then took significantly contrasting policies towards the Uniate Church^[1].
Within the 1839-1875 the Uniate Church in West Russian Empire were dissolved and incorporated into the Orthodox Church, while Austrian Galicia, the Uniate Church were treated as the equal of the Roman Catholic Church^[1].

The Uniate Church of Galicia helped influence in generation of nationalist feeling in western Ukraine. The Uniate Church became the national church of Galician Ukrainians owing to the fact that until IWW people's religious identities did not often correspond to their ethnic identity (chapter 3, p. 22^[1].) During IWW some Galicians converted to the Orthodox, while others were developed highlighted anti-Russian sentiments.

The highlighted territory of present-day Ukraine belongs to Russia:
•920-1596 (676 years)
•1772-1915 (143 years)
•1918-1991 (73 years)
In total, there are 892 years.

03.05.(09.06) 1815: Congress of Vienna.
Bessarabia, present-day Ukraine, and Moldova belongs to Russian Empire.

03.05.(09.06) 1815: Congress of Vienna.
Austria got to control Galicia.

„Ukrainian identity reflects a long history of tensions from competing Eastern/Russian/Orthodox and Western/Polish/Catholic political, cultural, religious, and social influences that continues to be felt today". (p. 30, chapter 4^[1].)
As a critical point, there is accepted the divided religious allegiances since 1596, due to the role of the Uniate Church from that time in forced Polonization and Latinization of the population of the Russian Empire. There is highlighted the great Polish political influence in the Uniate Church.

[1] Y. Aoshima, Entangled interactions between religions and national consciousness in Central and Eastern Europe, Academic Studies Press, Boston, 2020, [ISBN: 9781644693568].

1862
Russian Empire

1907-1914
Russian Empire

U(O)kraina (guberniia, province, oblast,)
(Created by Ekaterina II (Rus: Екатерина II; (Y)(E)c(h)aterine II) in 1764)

1764-1870
Russian Empire

East Ukraine - empty non-developed weak/lacking Russian Government (p. 182#)

1839: Uniate population is at about 300000 western Ukrainians.

No-man's land##

West Ukraine - relatively developed with Polish/German elites (p. 182#)

1794-1839: Mass conversions of Greek Catholics to Eastern Orthodoxy in central Ukraine, where the Uniate church had a relatively limited hold.

1783 (Separate citizenship): *Rossiyanin* – The word was used during the Russian Empire and refers today to citizens of the Russian Federation.

In total, in Russia were 59891069 people (1863).

Novorossiia (p. 508^[1])
1768: 52000 (males)
1772: 242000 people
1796: 835000 people
1812: 1.4 mln people

It belongs to Russian Empire in accordance with Kucuk-Kainardji Treaty (21.07.1774) and Article 7^{###}.

Novorossiia (Oblast, guberniya, province)
Created 1764

Novorossiia
1774: 4470302 Russian officers of the Empire were distributed.

Odessa
1802: 8000 people
1841: 73000 people
1856: 101302 people
1897: 403815 people

No-man's land

No-man's land

Mariupol (Zdanov, USSR) Katerynoslav province, 1784

1775 Zaporizhina was grown.

It belongs to Russian Empire in accordance with Jassy Treaty (1792).

Bessarabia (part)
1783: Bulgarian migrants (p. 507^[1])
1989: 65072 ethnic Bulgarians

Odessa (1794)

Taurida province, 1784

Taurida province
1783

1804: First Eastern Orthodox church

The etymology of the word O(U)kraj(i)na is „at the end of“....Russian Empire.

10.03.1779: Crimean Tatars were settled by a „Convention explicative“[#] Their personality, property, churches, and natural faith, which they can exercise freely and inviolably with all its legal rituals were defended by law.

[1] A. Bitis, The 1828–1829 Russo-Turkish war and the resettlement of Balkan peoples into Novorossiia. *Jahrbücher für Geschichte Osteuropas*. 53 (2005) 506–525 .

^{###} „Unsettled open steppe“ (p. 181 [T. Martin, The Empire's newfrontiers: New Russia's path from frontier to „Okraina“1774–1920. *Russian History*. 19 (1992) 181–201].)

^{###}R. Davison, Russian skill and Turkish imbecility”: The Treaty of Kuchuk Kainardji reconsidered [https://doi.org/10.2307/2495120].

[#]G. Noradounghian, *Recueil d'actes internationaux de l'Empire ottoman*, Paris (1897–1903), Vol. 1, pp. 338–344.

Ukrainians' claim: Zaporizhzhian territories belonged to the Sich, and, therefore to the Ukrainian people, including Kuban [page 273 #][#], where up to 1930 were claimed 71 % ethnics Ukrainians.

683-883 (Bochkove) *Saltiv Bulgars* (Proto-Bulgarians) R1a-M417 [6];
800-900 (Bochkove) *Saltiv Bulgars* U5a1a1 [6].

1766-1826 Russian Empire

16th-18th: Zaporizhzhian Cossacks were different ethnic group from the neighbouring Don Cossacks (p. 271#). The gene pool of Don Cossacks is to the gene pool of the East Slavs; a typical one for ethnic Russians showing haplogroup R1a1-M198 (p. 526 [2]). Consider, distribution and origin of people having haplohaplogroup R1a1-M198 in p. 30, Figure 4 [3], as well.
1874: There were ca. 40000 men, members of the Zaporozhian Host in Hetmán Bohdan Xmel'nyckyj's agreement with Polish-Lithuanian Kingdom in 1654. The document is regarded as less reliable one, since, there is a much larger Muscovy register showing ca. 127000 Zaporozhian Cossacks in 1654 [#]. Despite, there were used linguistic criteria showing that Ukrainian personal names cannot be proved from phonetics, due to parallel to Ukrainian sounds of also observed Russian equivalents. There were ca. 14 % Cossacks from Ukraine; 39 % from other countries (Moldavia, Crimea, Caucasus, etc.); 26 % Muscovy, and 17 % from Belarus, respectively. *Bulgarians* were 0.5% %.

In addition, Y-chromosomal haplogroups (in [%]) taken from Table 2 in work [1] of people from North Caucasus — the city Kuban belongs to the mentioned area, as well as — show that ethnic people *Shapsug*, *Abkhas*, and *Circassians* have within 20.7–86 % of P303 haplogroup (Table 2 [1])[###].

The former group people, i.e. *Shapsug* are the most numerous Circassian ethnics in Israel and third-most numerous ethnics in present-day Türkiye. The *Shapsugs* are regarded as ethnics rooting in a branch of Adyge people). *Circassian* people are also known as *Cherkess* or *Adyghe*. Their origin rooted in North Caucasus; near present-day Krasnodar region and city Kuban.

The G2a (P16) is typical for people from North Caucasus. It is only 17 % in Iranian people [4]. Ethnic Russians lack of both the P303 and P16 haplogroups (0%[±]). The G2a haplogroup of 1.5(1)% has been determined in citizens of Pskov (p.889#).

In ethnics *Balkars* it is 33.3–22.5 % (Table 2 [4],) while P303 is 21.4–6.0 %. The haplogroup G2a3b-P303 is a modal one for the western *Circassians* (70%).

Ethnic *Balkars* have been considered historical relatives of the *Volga Bulgars*. The G2a is found in *Balkarians* (22.5 %) from Caucasus, as well [4].

Looking at R_{ST} parameter — it evaluates haplotype diversity and distances among ethnic group peoples [2] — there is seen R_{ST} distances from Don Cossacks to *Abkhazians* (R_{ST}=0.213), *Azov Greeks* (R_{ST}=0.198), *Circassians* (R_{ST}=0.147), and Southern Russians (R_{ST}=0.0) [2]. It is R_{ST}=0.311 to *Shapsugs* [2]. Therefore, ethnic group people called Don Cossacks (16th-18th CE) are well-distinguished from ethnics rooting in North Caucasus, including *Saltiv Bulgars*. Despite, the fact that there are common haplogroups of human artifacts since Neolithic period near Mariupol [5] and *Saltiv Bulgars* within 800–900 BC near Bochkove [6].

1874: Migrants from Ukraine to the United States demonstrate high frequencies of haplogroup R1b (53.8–52.4%) and low frequencies of R1a (7.7–4.8). They are Mennonite community people with Y haplogroups J2 and G2a (p. 105, [7].)

1746: Elizaveta's decree granted the steppe on the east of river Kal'mius to the Don Cossacks.

1860: In Zaporizhzhina the Ukrainians were migrated since 1860*.

1200-1100: *Cumans*, N1a-Y10755 [5].
1300-1400: *Cumans*, J1c2e1 [6].
1400-1500: *Nogai*, G2a-Z6679 [8], J1a-Y5321, C2a-M504, R1b-Y14051.

Novorossia (Neolithic period): (mtDNA) U5a1a, C4a2, H5a [5].

"Zaporizhzhians never fixed their borders exactly." They were "without political or religious overton###".

Russia (2024): The number of respondents declaring themselves to be *Circassians* rose from 73184 (2010) to 115 000 (2021) [8]. *Circassian* nationalities, including *Kabardins*, *Adygs*, and *Shapsugs* declare their common ethnonym rather than the nationality [8]. There are at about 18.3 % mixed ethnics *Cherkessk**. (consider, further, thematic slide 2.)

Ukraine, 700-600 BC: *Scythian*, R1a-M420 [6].
Ukraine (East Dnieper), 2nd BC-4th A.D.: *Alans*, speaking Skytho-Sanati language dialects as *Digor* (West Ossetic) and *Iron* (East Ossetic) ones###.

1926: (Kuban region.) 1951000 Ukrainians[§].

#A. Wilson, Donbas between Ukraine and Russia: The Use of History in Political Disputes. *Journal of Contemporary History*. 30 (1995) 265-289.
[#] Zastavnyi (1992, op. cit.), 45-76; and Rostyslav Sossa (ed.), *Ukrainci: skhidna diaspora* (Kiev 1993); and Lavriv (1992, op. cit.), 119 (NB! The three references were cited in [4], however, are online unavailable).
#M. Chukhryaeva, E. Pavlova, V. Napoloskikh, et al. Is There a Finno-Ugric Component in the Gene Pool of Russians from Yaroslavl Oblast? Evidence from Y-Chromosome. *Russian Journal of Genetics*. 53 (2017) 388-399.
#B. Malyarchuk, M. Derenko, T. Grzybowski et al. Differentiation of Mitochondrial DNA and Y Chromosomes in Russian Populations. *Human Biology*. 76 (2004) 877-900.
##O. Balanovsky, K. Dibirova, A. Dybo et al. Parallel Evolution of Genes and Languages in the Caucasus Region, *Mol. Biol. Evol.* 28 (2011) 2905-2920.
#G. El'chinova, V. Kadyshev, R. Zinchenko et al. Immigration of the Russian Urban Population of the North Caucasus. *Russian Journal of Genetics*. 57 (2021) 978-981.
[###] S. Rootsi, N. Myres, A. Lin et al. Distinguishing the co-ancestries of European G Y-chromosomes in the populations of Europe and the Caucasus. *European Journal of Human Genetics* 20 (2012) 1275-1282.
#B. Struminsky, The Origins of the Zaporozhian Cossacks: Apropos of a Recent Study. *Harvard Ukrainian Studies*. 9 (1985) 182-197.
###O. Pritsak, J. Reshetar, Jr. The Ukraine and the Dialectics of Nation-Building. *Slavic Review* 22 (1963) 224-255.

[1] O. Balanovsky, K. Dibirova, A. Dybo et al. Parallel Evolution of Genes and Languages in the Caucasus. *Mol. Biol. Evol.* 28 (2011) 2905-2920.
[2] M. Chukhryaeva, I. Ivanov, S. Frolova et al. The Haplomatch Program for Comparing Y-Chromosome STR-Haplotypes and Its Application to the Analysis of the Origin of Don Cossacks. *Russian Journal of Genetics* 52 (2016) 521-529.
[3] O. Balanovsky, O. Utevska, E. Balanovska. Genetics of Indo-European populations: the past, the future. *Journal of Language Relationship* 9 (2013) 23-35 [ISSN 1998-6769].
[4] M. Dzhaubermeezova, N. Ekomasovaa, S. Litvinov et al. Genetic Characterization of Balkars and Karachays according to the Variability of the Y Chromosome. *Russian Journal of Genetics* 53 (2017) 1152-1158.
[5] A. Nikitin, J. Newton, I. Potekhina. Mitochondrial haplogroup C in ancient mitochondrial DNA from Ukraine extends the presence of East Eurasian genetic lineages in Neolithic Central and Eastern Europe. *Journal of Human Genetics* 57 (2012) 610-612
[6] L. Saag, O. Utevska, S. Zadnikov et al. North Pontic crossroads: Mobility in Ukraine from the Bronze Age to the early modern period. *BioRxiv* (2024) [doi: https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.05.24.595769].
[7] K. Beatty, M. Mosher, M. Crawford, P. Melton. Paternal Genetic Structure in Contemporary Mennonite Communities from the American Midwest. *Human Biology* 88 (2016) 95-108.
[8] B. Bowling. The impact (or not) of the war in Ukraine on Russian minorities and minorities policy. *European Yearbook of Minority* (2024) in press [ISSN 2211-6117] [https://eprints.bbk.ac.uk/id/eprint/52076].

§ V. Vublikov, *Journal of Frontier Studies*. (2022) (3) pp. 63 - 91.

1766-1826 Russian Empire

Thus, Zaporizhzhian Cossacks or Dnieper Cossacks (16th-18th CE), perhaps, rooted in *Circassians* ethnics (*Cherkessk, Adyghe*) including *Saltiv Bulgars*, despite the fact that there is found (2024) that Zaporizhzhian Cossacks and *Nogais* have similar ethnic identities and a common language structure[1]. Ethnic Nogai were also connected with North *Caucasus* and some *Nogai* terms originated from *Adygh*.

A study of Khazar elite burials (7th-9th CE) of present-day Rostov region shows artifacts that exhibit West Eurasian gene pool (G2a, R1a, R1b) [2].

Further: Genetic study of artifacts from Rétköz (Hungary) [3] shows R1a-Z93, N-M46, Q-M242, R1b-L23, and G2a-L156 haplogroups; thus, highlighting them as common to ancient *Xiongnu*, ancient *Avar*, Caucasian *Avar*, *Abkhazian*, *Balkarian*, and *Circassian* in agreement with the data on the thematic slide (1) (above). The highest frequency of G2a-P303 is connected with South Caucasian *Abkhazians* (24%), Northwest Caucasian *Adyghes* (39.7%), and Cherkessians (36.5%). There have been established haplogroups R1a-Z280 (19.8%), R1a-M458 (17%), R1b-P312 (12.3%), R1b-P25/M343 (7.55%), E1b1-M78 (6.6%), I2a-p37 (6.6%), G2a-L156 (6.6%), and I1-M253 (4.7%), respectively [3][###].

Therefore, the migrants from Ukraine to the United States in 1874, who show main haplogroups J2 and G2a (p. 105, [4]), cannot be connected with ethnic Ukrainians.

In-depth study of genetic pool of people (780 samples from 10 regional populations of *Kazakhs*, *Uzbeks*, *Turkmen*s, *Dungans*, and *Karakalpaks*) from Transoxiana – a historical region covering southwestern part of Central Asia [6] – shows haplogroup J2 (M172) in *Dungan* ethnics, *Uzbek*, and *Karakalpak*, while P303, P15, and M406 can be found in the same ethnic people together with *Turkmen* of *Yomut* tribe.

The frequency of G2-P15 haplogroup in Indian and Pakistan people is accounted for 1.24–4.55 % (Table 5 [7].) Ukrainians (154 males, Lviv) show E1b1b1, J2, R1a1a, R1a1a7, R1b1, R1b1a2, F*, K* [5].

There have been established some lineages; for instance, as J-M241 (J2b2) and E-V13 which are over-represented in the *Sibiu Basarab* comparing with Romanians, as well [8]. Data on *Bulgarians* are also shown. Haplogroups R1a1a-M17 and R1a1a7-M458 were found in *Ifov Basarab*, as well [8].

In particular, Zaporizhzhian Cossacks' colonel Ivan Volevačenko (1653) rooted in southeast Čerčasy according to document E 8548 of the archive of the Ottoman Empire*.

Haplogroup (sel.)	Ethnics			
	Balkars	Bulgarians	Ukrainians	Russians
Refs.	[S1]	(Figure 2 [S2])[S3]	[S4]	[S5][S6]
			[%]	
R1a-Z2123/M198	16.2	18.8 – 4.3	43.6(41)	60.9 – 36.2 ^{††}
R1b-M478	11.5			0.0
G2a-P16	22.5	0.4–0.0	9.6	0.0 ^{††††} (1.5 ^{†††} % Pskov)
G2a-P303	6.0	3.2–0.0	(M201/P15)	0.0
J2a-M410	15.3	2.2–0.0	11.7	0.0
J2b-M12 (M241)	1.7	1.6–0.0 (11.1–0.0)	(M89/J)	0.0
N3		0.6–0.0	9.6(4)	(79) 35.0 – 8.4 ^{††}

4230-3995 BC: The G2a-P303 haplogroup was found in ancient human male artifacts from Greece (sample Klei10 in Table S10***.) The haplogroup G2 and sub-lineages is typical for Neolithics humans from Greek peninsula; western Anatolia, southern Balkans, the Sea of Marmara; and central Europe***.

[S1] M. Dzhaubermezova, N. Ekomasova, S. Litvinov et al. Genetic characterization of Balkars and Karachays according to the variability of the Y chromosome. Russian Journal of Genetics 53 (2017) 1152–1158.
 [S2] S. Karachanak, V. Grugni, S. Fornarino et al. Y-Chromosome diversity in modern Bulgarians: New clues about their ancestry. PLOS ONE 8 (2013) e56779.
 [S3] S. Karachanak, V. Carossa, D. Nesheva, et al. Bulgarians vs the other European populations: A mitochondrial DNA perspective. International Journal of Legal Medicine 126 (2012) 497–503.
 [S4] V. Kharkov, V. Stepanov, S. Borinskaya, et al. Gene pool structure of Eastern Ukrainians as inferred from the Y-chromosome haplogroups. Russian Journal of Genetics 40 (2004) 326–331.
 [S5] I. Morozova, A. Evsyukov, A. Kon'kov et al. Russian ethnic history inferred from mitochondrial DNA diversity. American Journal of Physical Anthropology. 147 (2012) 341–351.
 [S6] M. Chukhryaeva, E. Pavlova, V. Napsolskikh et al. Is there a Finno-Ugric component in the gene pool of Russians from Yaroslavl oblast? Evidence from Y-chromosome. Russian Journal of Genetics. 53 (2017) 388–399.
 *M. Chukhryaeva, E. Pavlova, V. Napsolskikh, et al. Is There a Finno-Ugric Component in the Gene Pool of Russians from Yaroslavl Oblast? Evidence from Y-Chromosome. Russian Journal of Genetics. 53 (2017) 388–399.
 †B. Malyarchuk, M. Derenko, T. Grzybowski et al. Differentiation of mitochondrial DNA and Y chromosomes in Russian populations. Human Biology. 76 (2004) 877–900.
 ††N. Trofimova, S. Litvinov, R. Khusainova et al. Genetic characterization of populations of the Volga-Ural region according to the variability of the Y-chromosome. Russian Journal of Genetics. 51 (2015) 108–115.

[###] S. Rootsi, N. Myres, A. Lin et al. Distinguishing the co-ancestries of haplogroup G Y-chromosomes in the populations of Europe and the Caucasus. European Journal of Human Genetics 20 (2012) 1275–1282.
 *A. Riedlmayer, V. Ostapchuk, Bohdan Xmel'nyckyj and the Porte: A Document from the Ottoman Archives. Harvard Ukrainian Studies. 8 (1984) 453-473.
 ***Z. Hofmanova, S. Kreutzer, G. Hellentha et al. Early farmers from across Europe directly descended from Neolithic Aegeans. Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA 113 (2016) 6886-6891.

[1] A. Ainabek, B. Abdualiuly, K. Molgazhdarov, B. Artymbayeva et al. Effects of Language Learning Strategies on Teaching Toponyms and Folk Geography Terms in Kazakh and Nogai Languages. Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies. 11 (2024) 140–163.
 [2] I. Kornienko, T. Faleeva, T. Schurr et al. Y-Chromosome haplogroup diversity in Khazar burials from Southern Russia. Russian Journal of Genetics. 57 (2021) 477–488.
 [3] H. Pamjav, A. Fóthi, D. Dudás et al. The paternal genetic legacy of Hungarian-speaking Rétköz (Hungary) and Váh valley (Slovakia) populations Front. Genet. 13 (2022) 977517.
 [4] K. Beaty, M. Mosher, M. Crawford, P. Melton, Paternal genetic structure in contemporary mennonite communities from the American Midwest. Human Biology 88 (2016) 95–108.
 [5] M. Mielnik-Sikorska, P. Daga, M. Wozniak et al. Genetic data from Y chromosome STR and SNP loci in Ukrainian population. Forensic Science International: Genetics 7 (2013) 200–203.
 [6] M. Zhabagin, E. Balanovska, Z. Sabitov et al. The Connection of the Genetic, Cultural and Geographic Landscapes of Transoxiana. Scientific Reports 7 (2017) 3085.
 [7] S. Sengupta, L. Zhivotovskiy, R. King. Polarity and temporality of high-resolution Y-chromosome distributions in India identify both indigenous and exogenous expansions and reveal minor genetic Influence of central asian pastoralists, The American Journal of Human Genetics. 78 (2006) 202–221.
 [8] B. Martinez-Cruz, M. Ioana, F. Calafell, Y-Chromosome Analysis in Individuals Bearing the Basarab Name of the First Dynasty of Wallachian Kings. PLoS ONE 7 (2012) e41803.

1775-1796 Russian Empire

Polygon
area = 15.1545

Kiev

Little Russia
(Oblast, province)

Polygon
area = 28.7363

1796: Kiev - Main city of the
guberniia Little Russia (province)***

***The map is adapted to: J. le Donne, The Territorial Reform of the Russian Empire 1775-1796. II: The Borderlands, 1777-1796. Cahiers du Monde russe et soviétique, 24 (1983) 411-457 (p. 421).

1880-1897 Russian Empire

*G. Surh, Ekaterinoslav City in 1905: Workers, Jews, and Violence, Int. Labor and Working-Class History. 64 (2003) 139-166
[1] V. Bublikov, Journal of Frontier Studies. (2022) (3) pp. 63 - 91.

Taurida province

It belongs to Russian Empire, due to Kucuk-Kainardji Treaty (21.07.1774) and Article 7.

14.11.1779: The law by Ekaterina II treats religious freedom of emigrants in empty Crimea and Azov areas.

19th CE: In Crimea, word *Tat* was used to people in South Crimea speaking Turco-Tatar dialect#. It lacks affiliation, origin, and original native tongue according to Ottoman Empire administration (before 1783) (*tat-ağası*###). The administration of the so-called *Crimean Khanate* before 1783 (a pre-feudal state) incorporated holdovers from the Mongol Golden Horde Empire. The term *Tat* is also used to *Goths* speaking Germanic‡. The group people *Tatars*^[1] were population lacking statehood neither during Empire of Golden Horde, nor during Ottoman Empire period, or Russian Empire one. The same is true for their statehood during Soviet Russia or present-day Russia, because of Republic Tatarstan do not represent State of group people Tatars from Crimea, despite the fact that there is Tatars 53.99 % majority population in present-day Republic Tatarstan* (ethnic Russian are 39.5 % and Chuvashs are 3.35 %.) The doubt is regarding *monoethnicity* of group people *Tatars* in Crimea (16th) and *indigeneity* of modern Tatars in Crimea.

1778: Crimea became empty (p. 5^[4].)

1774: 18407 Greeks in South Crimea
1774: The *Tat* settlers were from Sudaq(k).

1784-1790: There were 1 mln people; 300 000 (30 %) were *Tatars*^[1]. The meaning of words *Tatars*, *Qıpçaqs* (*Kıpçak*), and *Qumans* heavily depend on place and time of their occurrences (p.269^[2].) The term *Tatar* is a rather common connotation in all people of Mongol Golden Horde Empire. It refers (13-14th CE) to *Qumans*, *Alans*, *Cherkess* ethnics, among others of Mongol Golden Horde Empire, rather than to west *Türks*#. If group people called *Tatars* is accepted as descendants of Golden Horde and *Crimean Khanate* (p. 102)^[3]; then, *Tatars* denote a multi-ethnic group people.

988: King Vladimir was baptized (p. 2^[4]).
27.07.988(?): Kherones was captured by King Vladimir (p.199 [5]).

Sevastopol'

212 A.D.: It was found by ethnic Alans^[2] (Iranian ethnic group people).

1764-1936 Russian Empire/Soviet Russia

1775 Zaporizhina was grown.

08.04.1783 (p. 2^[4])
No-man's land
(empty, inhabitable)

19th CE: In Mariupol' the word *Tat* was used to people speaking Greek#. The Turkish speaking population were called *bazarian*.

Present-day:
Zaporizhzhia
(Zaporozhskaia Sech')

Mariupol'

Medieval texts show group people called *Tat*, who have found along: (a) Sea of Azov as speaking Greek people; (b) Caspian Sea as people, speaking Persian; and (c) in the Roumanian and Bulgaria (mainly in Dobrudja) as people speaking *Tatar* (p. 77#). The word *Tat* often refers to west *Türks* and can be found in early Turkic sources, but it is not used in Chag(h)atay^{***} writings (1227); writings during Karakhanid period (992-1212), and *Türkish* literature after the medieval period (see, below.) Also, the word *Tat* was used to all kind of subjects, who were alien to Turco-Tatar tribes##. In Central Asia the word *Tat* was replaced with ethnic term Tajik. **Word/term *Tat* was used to all Muslims in South Crimea, as well.**

Crimea

1810: Crimea „was given to Tatars by Ekaterina II“ among other multi-ethnics groups people, because of 1545 there were only 3.3 % group people called Tatars in Crimea; furthermore, with doubtful *monoethnicity* and *indigeneity* (next slide.)

6th CE B.C. Scythian in Crimea

3rd-4th CE. Crimea was Greek (multi-ethnic) colony (stateless territory.)

733-746: Crimea become colony (multi-ethnic stateless territory) of the Byzantine Empire. The nomadic people in Crimea were mainly *Huns*, *Onogur-Bulgars*, *Khazars*, *Pechenegs*, *Greeks*, *Armenians*, *Qumans*, and more^[2]. The *Qumans* were associated with ethnics *Qıpçaqs*, as well.

Feodosiya
16th CE:
Kefe/Kaffa

6th C.E.: The first Capital of old Bulgarian Empire

9th: *Тьму-торокаль* (the old name of the city) east Slavic language; „каль“ - means ten thousand people; there were Rus' and Greek local cultures

Panagoria

Taman (present-day)
It is known since 51 A.D.

Sudaq(k)
Old-Russian: Surož'

[1] *Bol'shaia Sovietskaia Entsiklopediia XXXV (1937) 279–324 (1st Ed.)*

[2] I. Vásáry, Orthodox Christian Qumans and Tatars of the Crimea in the 13th–14th centuries. *Central Asiatic Journal* 32 (1988) 260–271.

[3] V. Vardys, The case of the Crimean Tartars. *The Russian Review* 30 (1971) 101–110.

[4] A. Schönle, Garden of the Empire: Catherine's appropriation of the Crimea. *Slavic Review*. 60 (2001) 1–23.

***Chaghatay (Tschagatai Khan, 1242) is the second son of Dschingis Khan (1227). Under Chag(h)atay writings often is understood any form of written Turkik text [L. Johanson, É. Csató (Eds.) *The Turkic Languages* (Routledge Language Family Series) 2nd.Ed. (2021) ISBN: 9780415738569]

*1920: There was created Tatar Autonomous Soviet Socialistic Republic; since, 02.1994 there is bilateral Treaty between Russian Federation and Republic Tatarstan.

#B. Williams, The Ethnogenesis of the Crimean Tatars. An Historical Reinterpretation. *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 11 (2001) 329-348.

#E. Schuetz, The Tat people on Crimea, *Acta Orientalia Academiae Scientiarum Hungaricae* 131 (1977) 77-106.

##Klaproth, *Zap. Imp. AN XXIV (1874) 55.*

###V. Kondaraki, *Universalnjoje opisanie Kryma*, SPbg 1895.

[5] A.Poppe, *The Political Background to the Baptism of Rus': Byzantine-Russian Relations*

Present-day:
Zaporizhzhia
(Zaporozhskaia Sech')

No-man's land
(empty, inhabitable)

16th CE: There are only two valuable censuses dealing with Crimea during Ottoman Empire (1529, 1545)^{###}. As major ethnic groups were listed *Greeks*, *Armenians*, and *Jews* as well as other people shown as "*Muslims*" (pp. 156-159.) There were mentioned few communities of *Tatars* as following: (a) 125 people (Kefe); 30 people in city Balıkklağu; and (c) 850 people in Azak district.

There were 1005 people called *Tatars* or 3.3 % minority (1545). In total, there were 30122 people in Crimea (1545). The largest city was Kefe, having 17302 people. The *Muslims* were minority at about 23.1%, despite, increasing in numbers of *Muslims* to at about 89 % since 1475. Until 1475 Crimea is Christianity colony.

460: *Bulgars*^{††}.

567: *Gök (Kök)-Türks (Tujuł)*, Khazars (amalgamated *Sabirs*, *Gök-Türks*, *Oghurs*, and *Önggüt* (from North Iran and Afghanistan)), *Qıpçaqs (Kıpçak)*.

Population in city Kefe (1545)	Number	[%]
Muslims		
Muslims	7348	42.47
41. Quarter of Tatars residing at Gül near Kefe	90	0.50
Non-Muslims		
Greeks	1885	10.89
Armenians	5922	34.23
Jews	799	4.62
73. Community of Circassian "penah"	320	1.85
74. Community of Rusyan [†]	147	0.85
76. Community of Circassian Jews	15	0.09

[†]Ukrainians were called *Rusyan* in Ottoman Empire

Population in Crimea (1936) [%]	1917 [1]	1936 [2] (p. 102)
Russians	50	43.5
Tatars		23.1
Ukrainians	25	10.0
Jews		7.4
Germans		5.7
Bulgarians		10.3 %
Czechs		
Estonians		
Others		

1929-1930: In Crimea at about 30000-40000 Tatars were deported to Ural or Siberia [*Sotsialisticheskii Vesnik, Paris, March 1950, pp. 51-52.*]

1936: In total, Crimea population: 875000; of who Tatars minority - 202000 (23.1%)[†]

The data seek to grasp terms *Tatar* and *Tat (Thatt)* used to population in Crimea from perspective of legal terms *ethnic* and *minority group* people; and *indigenous* population. The highlights are on so-called *Crimea Tatars* — often shown as *Osmanli* or *Ottomans*[†], because of Crimean Tatars were exiled from Crimea (1930 and 1944) and are classified as *indigenous people* of the peninsula[†](p. 329). Crimean Tatars' ethnogenesis (13th CE) is traced nomadic Mongols, despite efforts to trace them to a pre-Mongolian ethnics, as well[†]. The ethno-history of Crimean Tatars is complex. Their language contains elements of both *Oghuz* Turkic and *Kıpçak* one. The ethnicity of modern Tatars of Russian Federation are well determined (p. 79^[3]). **The Tatar language is the second most commonly used spoken language of European Union^[5].**

However, con-arguments that modern Crimean Tatars are the same people called Crimea Tatars in 16th CE strike the reader looking at data on the only two valuable censuses dealing with Crimea population during Ottoman Empire (1529, 1545)^{####}. There were two groups *Muslim* people "*Muslims*" and "*Tatars*". The latter group, however, were minority (3 %) 1005 people (1545). Thus, statement that "...great Tatar clans in Crimean peninsula" traced back in 1420-1430 had begun to contemplate separation from the Great Horde people[†] is obviously wrong.

Further: The statement that at the end of 13th CE many peoples including *Goths* become *Tatarized* and were converted to Islam and become *Tatars* is also wrong[†], because of this means that *Tat*-people in old Turkic texts were the same as *Tatars* in Ottoman texts. However, in 1396 *Tatars* had used term *Tat* to describe Islamized *Goths*[†]. Therefore, the old *Tats* cannot be associated with *Tatars* (1545) of Ottoman censuses. There is also highlighted anthropological differences between *Tatars* and *Tats*. The former people had round faced, short and dark, while *Tats* had high stature, fair hair and blue eyes[†]. However, other source describes *Qıpçaqs* as having blue eyes and red hair, as well^{†††}. If there is accepted the latter statement as a true one; thus, distinguishing between *Tat-Tatars* and *Qıpçaqs-Tatars*[†] then *Qıpçaqs-Tatars* cannot be accepted as *indigenous* people of Crimea, because of their origin, therein, dates since 567. Even, if there is associated term *Tatars* (1545) with *Kök* (or *Gök*) Turks, then, again, their origin traced back in 567.

Conversely, the presence of *Bulgars* in Crimea dates since 460-470^{††} or at about 100 years earlier. Next, if under term *Tat-Tatars*[†] in Crimea, there is understood Islamized *Greek-Goths* who were described as majority dynasties during that time, then, again there is discrepancy with Ottoman censuses, because of, in fact, in 1545 Armenians were larger population ethnic group in Crimea.

There is also thing with argument that *Crimea Tatars* (1545) were *Osmanli* or *Ottomans*[†], due to problem with explaining ethnic origin of Ottomans. There are two hypotheses (next slide.) Despite, if there is accepted that *Ottomans* originated from *Oghuz*-people; and, therefore there is accepted the view that they were descendants of Seljuk Sultanate in Anatolia (1077-1308), then according to work^[4], *Oghuzs* were Azeris of Caucasus, who were migrated into Anatolia in 1077 and than to Crimea in 1475 with the Golden Horde. In 1243 the Seljuk Sultanate becomes Mongolian vassal state, while in 1308 Anatolia becomes Mongolian province. Thus, Crimean Tatars should originate in this case in Crimea since 1475; and, they again, cannot be classified as *indigenous* population. To this argument could be added the following: The *Tatar* ethnonym is connected with both *Turkik* (Ottoman text, 1545) and *Ta-Tan* or Mongols (Chinese^[6]).

[†]B. Williams, The Ethnogenesis of the Crimean Tatars. An Historical Reinterpretation. Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society 11 (2001) 329-348.

^{††}J. Lee, The Turkic Peoples in World History, Routledge (2023) [ISBN: 9781032188379].

^{†††}(a)J. Asian Civilization 36 (2013) 189, (b) I. Zimonyi, The Origin of Volga Bulgars, Studia Uralo-Altaica 32 [ISSN 0133-4239][https://acta.bibl.u-szeged.hu/38748/1/altaica_032.pdf]

[1] *Politiccheskii Dnevnik, April 1970, p. 3.*

[2] V. Vardys, The case of the Crimean Tatars. The Russian Review 30 (1971) 101-110.

[3] E. Баландовская, А. АгджоянМ. Жабагин, et al. ТАТАРЫ ЕВРАЗИИ, АНТРОПОЛОГИЯ (Вестник Московского университета. Серия XXII) (2)(2016) 75–85.

[4] J. Lee, S. Kyoung, A Comparative Analysis of Chinese Historical Sources and Y-DNA Studies with Regard to the Early and Medieval Turkic Peoples. Inner Asia 19 (2017) 197-239.

^{####}A. Fisher, The Ottoman Crimea in the sixteenth Century. Harvard Ukrainian Studies 5 (1981) 135-170.

Ukraine

Old: Taurida province

2001

Zaporizhzhia

2001: 45 % of pre-, primary and secondary schools were officially using Ukrainian.
55 % education in Russian language.

2001: 0.8 % of pre-, primary and secondary schools were officially using Ukrainian.
99.2 % education in Russian language.

Ethnicity¹:
Russians (58.5%)
Ukrainians (24.4%) and Crimean Tatars (12.3%).
The Russian language dominates: 77.0%

Ethnicity²:
Russians (60.4%)
Ukrainians (24.1%) and Crimean Tatars (10.21%).
Other minority ethnic groups (5.37%).

In total, Crimea population: 2024000¹ people

In total, Sevastopol's population: 379500¹ people

In total, Sevastopol' and Crimea population: 2403500¹ or 2401200² (2001) people

Crimea

Sevastopol'

1948: A city with Russian Republican subordination.

**1829-1915
Russian Empire**

**Belarus
(Oblast)**

Gubernii: Podolia,
Volhynia

**Ukraine
(Oblast)**

Gubernii: Taurida,
Yekaterinoslav, and
Kherson

According to: *Europäisches Russland; Stieler's Schul-Atlas (Justus Perthes 1829), Suppl. III: Gubernii: Kiev, Chernigov, Poltava, and Kharkov.*

1915: Ukraine's Claim to Freedom *via* pamphlet published by New Jersey's Ukrainian National Association and Pennsylvania's Ruthenian National Union, demanding autonomy for Russian Ukraine and "a self-governed province ... not dominated by the Poles or their aristocracy."

Galicia (1880): Ukrainian speaking province ‡

Ratio (Speaking Ukrainian/Speaking Polish)

‡The map is adapted to W. Włoskiewicz, *Names: A Journal of Onomastics*, 71 (2023) 20-39 [DOI 10.5195/names.2023.2598].

1829-1915 Russian Empire

19th CE (end): Galicia become an arena of ethnic conflict among Poles, Ukrainians, and Jews, regarding not only issues of politics, but also economic, cultural, educational, and religious ones (p.152^[1].) Polish nationalism played a crucial role in the province far before its autonomy. The Ukrainian nationalism took shape later.

Lviv
(Lemberg/
Lwow)

1910: 105469 (51.17%) Poles; 39314 (19.07%) Ukrainians; in total 206133 people (p.151^[1]).

Bukovina: It belongs to Austro-Hungarian Empire 1774+(5[#])-1918.

It belongs to Bessarabia until 1947

1910: Multi-ethnics: Ukrainians, Polish, Germans, Hungarians, and Rumenians.

1738: Bukovina is met first as districts under Polish and Moldavian administration.

‡The maps are adapted to K. Scharr, Die Landschaft Bukowina, Boehlau Verlag Wien, 2010 [ISBN: 9783205784630].
*P. Gheorghie, P. Alexandra, 16th Int. Multidisciplinary Scientific GeoConference SGEM 2016, pp. 611-618.

[1] Y. Aoshima, Entangled interactions between religions and national consciousness in Central and Eastern Europe, Academic Studies Press, Boston, 2020, ISBN: 9781644693568.

Russian Empire 20.11.1917

Ukraine
(Third Universal;
Basic Eight)

On **20.11.1917**, there was proclaimed a short-lived **Ukrainian People's Republic**, whose independence, however would be achieved "**without separating from the Russian Republic and destroying its unit**".

There are so-called basic eight gubernii (areas, oblasti):

Kiev, Podolia, Volhynia, Chernigov, Poltava, Kharkov, Yekaterinoslav, and Kherson, respectively.

The Sun (22 July 1917), 9: Ukraine consists of five provinces, *i.e.* Podolia, Kiev, Chernigov, Poltava and Kharkov, respectively.

Neue Zeitung (05.01.1918) : Ukraine consists of the basic eights provinces and Taurida one (without Crimea).

The Ukraine claim is for ethno-territory non-congruent with gubernii boundaries.

On **09.02.1918**, the Central Powers have formally recognized Ukrainian Rada with a peace Bread Peace Treaty. It describes the Ukrainian frontier *via* Article II. Section (a) reaffirmed the prewar frontier between Habsburg and Romanov monarchies. Section (b) define frontier between Ukraine and the Regency Kingdom of Poland. Other frontiers are not specified.

Russian Empire 1917-1920

Gubernii/territory of the provinces

After I WW the self-determination was declared as an imperative principle of action (Peace Conference of Paris, 1919). Due to significant dynamics of events the post-war borders of Eastern Europe proved extremely difficult for decision-makers. There is controversy of available war-time maps of the region.

02.11.1917 (15.11.1917?): Declaration of rights of people of Russia;
More than 40 provinces were self-determined, including forming of separate States of the territory of the former Russian Empire

10.12.1918: Bessarabia autonomy[#] was abolished.
Paris, Peace Conference, 1919: Bessarabia become part of Romania

1897: 3000000 inhabitants; of them 2000000 Romanians (Moldovans) (47.6%)

1919: Polish annexed Zhytomyr and Eastern Galicia provinces; The annex is recognized in 1923 from France, UK, and USA.

Within the framework of the Russian Empire, the Bessarabians called themselves Moldovans due to the name of the historical Principality of Moldova.

In Romanian and Russian they were called Bessarabians.

There is regional, rather than ethnic identity of people.

Bessarabia/Basarabia province (Russian guberniia)

Paris Treaty (28.10.1920) Bessarabia is recognized as part of Romania.

Principality Moldova

Transnistria

Bessarabia
(It belongs to Russian Empire with Bucharest Treaty 1812.)
(Consider original map of 1862, above.)

Moldovans people (1920) [%]
(Bessarabia)

1918

Romania

[#]The term "Autonomy" refers to a special status of a region within an otherwise unitary (noncomposite) state (G. Mirsky, Chapter 3: On Some Aspects of Ethnic Conflicts; In On Ruins of Empire: Ethnicity and Nationalism in the Former Soviet Union (1997) [ISBN: 978-0-313-30044-8], p.58.)

Romania: NATO Member State
(Region: Balkan, East-Europe)

Slovakia: NATO Member State
(Region: Central-East-Europe)

Slovakia

Hungary

Romania

In **1923 USSR** (instead of **RSFSR**) have been organized as soft-Federation of Republics based on titular nationalities.
Word „*Russia*” was not been used, despite the ethnic majority Russians in USSR, by Stalin. This decision was not been changed by Lenin, despite, his opposed choice, *i.e.* RSFSR. There was mainly Ukrainian primacy of the issue and the so-called national question.

1926: 7.8 mln citizens defined themselves as Ukrainians.
1937: 3 mln citizens defined themselves as Ukrainians.

Economic warfare against Soviet Russia (G4 decision on 09.05.1919.)
There was extremely difficult to import goods for many months

30.12.1922: RSFSR (USSR; Soviet Russia) had/have been socio-political system: Soft-federation, who are dissolved by Belavezha Accords (08.12.1991).

[1] A. Wierzbicki, Ethnicity and Power in the Soviet Union. Post-Soviet Issues. 4 (2017) 240–255 [DOI: 10.24975/2313-8920-2017-4-3-240-255].

Author's note (1)

Since, the author's aim is not just to inform the reader about events from history of Europe, but to focus his, respectively, her attention on problems of victimology in context of the purpose of the contribution, at this point it might be useful to give an account of doctrines used as an attempt to understand, even, explain the logic of historical events of IWW and IIWW as well as their mutual connection; if any. The IIWW was the most terrible war not only from perspective of European history, but also from perspective of the World one. There are a set of doctrines, due to enormous work over decades. Further, they are extended over a lot of years and are frequently changed; thus, inventing new arguments, dropping arguments from old facts, handling historical events in a variety of mainly policy context as in the case of Ukraine-Russia conflict (2014–2024). There is needed a serious understanding of past events involving Ukraine and Russia in order to provide adequate and objective conclusion from legal point of view regarding victims (Russians and their State Russia) of the latter conflict (2014–2024).

Thus, it must be highlighted that formally the IWW begins with 28.06.1914. It is also claimed that the IWW begins with date 08.1914.

Formally, it ended in 11.11.1918; thus dissolving four of centuries-old land dynastic empires — the Ottoman, Habsburg, and Romanov (Russian Empire) empires together with Hohenzollern one. Their territories almost completely vanished from the map. The Treaty of Lausanne (29.10.1923) defined the territory of present-day Türkiye. The Hohenzollern empire, occupied enormous area of Central-East Europe was reduced in size and transformed into a parliamentary democracy often referred to as so-called bleeding frontier toward the East. Thus, IWW took another decades and IIWW (1939–1945) to the process of European imperial dissolution. The IWW (1911–1923) remains nutshell of the latter process.

Therefore, the shown social-processes in Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic within 1922–1933 are not stand-alone ones. They are results from new socio-political order in Europe from mainly imperial state as form of territorial governance to a nation-state socio-political system which was on the rise, during that time.

The latter paragraph is a common argumentative approach to history of Europa over the discussed period, political sciences, and even philosophy of the science which claims to proceed a lot of events happened during that time, and in fact it does proceed by answering the most important question of how Nazi-regime was established in Germany and some European States during 1933–1945?

Perhaps, useful works to Author's note would be^[1-7] ones together with cited references, therein. Particularly, work^[1] comprehensively details on so-called *classical* assumptions framing history of IWW, which is regarded as an object of an in-depth historical research, with an explicit remark that the impact is given on West-European States.

There is a dominating assumption that after IWW there are, in fact, epicenters of a cycle of armed conflicts, particularly, highlighting continued massive violences until 1923 when the new Republic Türkiye was established; Greek's conflict; Irish Civil War, and more (pp. 787–788^[1]) causing for a large number of ethnic conflicts in Europa and Near East. The highlights are on widespread and massive crimes during 1918–1928 in Türkiye when 70000 people died (30000 Greeks were massacred in 1922 in Smyrna by Turkish troops), at about 900000 Christians and 400000 Greek Muslims were resettled, forcibly (p. 794^[1].) The latter events are regarded as the largest forced population transfer in the European history until IIWW.

Thus, the IWW and post-war conflicts and violence are linked with a highlighted destabilizing effect on legitimacy and authority of many European countries, where as an effort to restore order there were established a dominance of different paramilitary structures (military or quasi-military organizations and their practices)^[2]. From the perspective of the purpose of the current contribution, there should be underlined the fact that in Germany, but not only (see^[2]), the paramilitary structures were transformed into ultra-nationalist terror organizations committing violence and affecting on many countries including Russia, Ukraine, the Baltic states, Poland, Austria, Hungary, Germany, Italy, Anatolia, and Caucasus, respectively^[3]. The so-called *Freikorps* in both Germany and Austria crushed the Munich Soviet republic in 1925^[2]. The paramilitary structures as armed political structures, however, organized on military lines become nutshell of Nazi-regime in Germany (1933–1945)^[3]. Their committed ethnic crimes are connected with the foundation of new nation-states; thus, replacing the old European Empires^[3].

(Author's remark on^[3]: The latter statement is wrong, regarding, the *Herrenvolk-Untermenschen* paradigm of Nazi-ideology of dominating ethnic group in Germany. Furthermore, the date 30.08.1914 is associated with the Polish-German conflict and the theory of *Pan-Germans* (p. 468^[4]) and establishment of Germans throughout the World which was detailed on O. Tannenbergs' book entitled „Gross Deutschland“ (1911). In the same battle-fields the Knights of the Teutonic Order were annihilated by the Poles on 15.07.1410. Work^[4] dating since 1918 even states for "colonial exploitation" of Ukraine by Germany (p. 480). Therefore, the colonization policy of the German-State and claims for their ethnic dominance during that time are well-documented. The conflicts between Germans and Poles is regarded as phenomenon dating since the Middle Ages (p. 182^[5].)

In addition to, manage to establish collaborative network among European countries ruled *via* Nazi-like regimes during 1920-1936, that grew exponentially; thus, becoming a vehicle for political ideas of European, and even universal ideology, during that time (p.11^[6]).

Despite, this classical doctrine seems to have key answers to a large number of questions, regarding events during IWW it could be terribly misleading as doctrine addressing social-processes in Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic within 1922–1933. Of course, they are, again, not stand-alone processes. However, they are linked with different facts from the European history shown in the next slides, where are given a bare summary of facts about events in Ukraine not only during IWW, but also postwar ones until 2014, because of ethnopolitical conflicts of different types have increased in the post-IWW in Soviet Russia^[7].

The aim is at providing objective pro-arguments and facts as well as taking a position about the truth of the claim that both ethnic Russians and State Russia can be classified as victims of Ukraine-Russia conflict (2014-2024). The focus is not only of the latter conflict, but also crimes of IWW committed against Russians in the territory of Ukraine and involving so-called Ukrainian State during that time.

A particular remark on crimes committed during the IWW should be that the contribution compulsorily excludes from neglecting, justifying, excusing, and the like crimes committed by Nazi-State. Rather, it highlights *Reichskommissariat* Ukraine as co-perpetrator State of crimes against ethnic-Russians, not only as Soviet soldiers (2000000 people), but also as Slav civilian population (3000000 people) (below) as well as, again, but in this case as perpetrator State-Ukraine of crimes against Russians and State Russia during the last conflict Ukraine-Russia (2014-2024). Problems, about arguments in the former case; if any, seem to make distinction among administrative functions of Nazi-military staff members (*Gebietekommissare*), who were mainly ethnic Germans; camp-policemen, who were mainly German-Ukrainians and Ukrainians; and Organization of Ukrainian Nationalists, who were mainly Ukrainians of this so-called *Reichskommissariat* Ukraine.

However, the contribution mainly attempts to highlight the general framework of anti-Russians and anti-State Russia crimes committed over decades; thus, linking them and providing facts and pro-arguments — pro-arguments and facts can be further gained, respectively, provided by archives of the Soviet Russia within 1945–1991 and archive of Nazi-regime within 1933–1945 of present-day Germany — about aforementioned claim, regarding victimology of Ukraine-Russian conflict (2014–2024).

Certainly, pressure is put on the latter case to the point that both the Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic and present-day State Russia are explored as so-called consuming space in a context of material resource, physical environment, and mental structure incorporating a shaping, rhetoric, and many Centuries sharply different socio-political systems of territorial governance; and thus, there is excluded from assumption that such a State — both the Soviet Russia and present-day Russia — can become a State-victim. The author works out of this view, however. The contribution deals only with facts and arguments in the context of its major goal, as entitled.

Useful references to author's note (1)

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[3] R. Gerwarth, J. Horne, Vectors of Violence: Paramilitarism in Europe after the Great War, 1917–1923. *The Journal of Modern History*. 83 (2011) 489–512.

[4] J. Brunhes, C. Vallaux, German Colonization in Eastern Europe. *Geographical Review* 6 (1918) 465 – 480.

[5] Y. Aoshima, Entangled interactions between religions and national consciousness in Central and Eastern Europe, Academic Studies Press, Boston, 2020, [ISBN: 9781644693568].

[6] M. Albanese, P. del Hierro. Chapter 1: The Origins of the Fascist Network, 1922–1936, In *Transnational Fascism in the Twentieth Century: Spain, Italy and the Global Neo-Fascist Network*, London, Bloomsbury Academic (2016) [http://dx.doi.org/10.5040/9781474219273].

[7] G. Mirsky, Chapter 3: On Some Aspects of Ethnic Conflicts, In *On Ruins of Empire: Ethnicity and Nationalism in the Former Soviet Union* (1997) Contributions in Political Science. Bloomsbury Collections [ISBN: 978-0-313-30044-8].

1938-1940

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR) (Russia)

Bolsheviks - captured Red Army soldiers (Russian, *boitsy*) and commanders (*komandiry*.)

Minsk
Novinki

Mogilëv

23.10.1941: 279 Jewish killed.

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR) (Russia) 1941

Reichskommissariat Ukraine
(Created 09.1941-09.1942)

18.09.1941: 200 patients (Slavs) were murdered.

02.10.1941: 2273 Russian prisoners were killed.
19.10.1941: 3726 Russian prisoners were killed.

Volodymyr-Volyns'kyi

District of Nazi Reich

Right Bank

Kiev

Left Bank

26.09.1941: 665000 Soviet prisoners captured.

Camp Stalag 365: Prisoners from Dnieper Ukrainian Red Army commanders have been declared by the Bandera faction of the Organization of Ukrainian Nationalists.

Uman'

08.1941: 103000 Soviet prisoners captured.

Reichskommissariat Ukraine was ruled by German military men (*Gebietekommissare*); camp policemen, and Organization of Ukrainian Nationalists, declared themselves as Bandera faction (Camp policemen: Ukrainians, Russians, Uzbeks, and Kazakhs.)

Nazi military rule (09.1941-09.1942)

> 310000 Ukrainians were recruitment by the German army as a *Hilfswilliger (Hiwi)* - a "voluntary helper"

"...Russian military men in captivity were brutally treated everywhere... Those prisoners, mistreated and killed by the millions, were not simply casualties of "war." Their captors could have prevented the mass prisoner mortality. The prisoner transports actually were death marches."

75 % Soviet military men (200000 (p.89)) were victims of genocidal massacre as war-prisoners.

Melitopol

10.10.1941: 100000 Soviet prisoners captured.

1941/1942: 2000000 Russians (Soviet) prisoners (non-Jewish) were victims of genocidal case of extermination policy (massacre.) From Nazi perspective Slavs were racially inferior. The IIWW was „war of extermination“. The racism was motor behind destroying Russians during IIWW.

10.10.1941: 100000 Soviet prisoners captured.

Kerch

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR) (Russia)

1941

Reichskommissariat Ukraine
(Created 09.1941-09.1942)

15-16.09.1941: 10000 Jews were murdered near Berdychiv

District of Nazi Reich

Right Bank

1941: Famine, due to Nazi starvation policy toward the capital and depopulating „Russian“ cities..

1941: 850000 people; ca. 50 % Ukrainians; 25 % Jews; and 16.67 % Russians..

1941: Tshemerinsk or Stalindorf (1928) was Jewish village. The Jews were resettled and replaced with ethnic German settlers....*“Ukrainian population was happy to have been delivered from the Jewish yoke“.*

Kiev

Left Bank

16.09.1941: 1875 victims of mass killing of who 79 % Jewish and 205 people Soviet (Russians according to few documents) citizens.

19.08.1941: 15000 Jews were murdered in Vinnytsia

01.09.1941: 23600 Jews were murdered in Kamianets-Podolsk

08.1942: executions of people from villages determined as "Racial Category IV" according to Herrenvolk-Untermenschen paradigm (low level racial purity or ideological conformity). (Kommando Dr. K. Stumpp, German Academics-ethno-political advisor, Ukrainian German)

Nazi military rule (09.1941-09.1942)

Kalinin

11.1941: Kommando Dr. K. Stumpp, German Academics-ethno-political advisor, Ukrainian German; He has made the "racial" composition of villages in Western Ukraine as part of process of determining Soviet Union's ethnic Germans.
1966: The Federal Republic of Germany awarded Dr. K. Stumpp with Distinguished Cross of Merit, First Class.

In 1942 Kommando Dr. Stumpp's statistics shows extermination actions of 259 villages: (1) Districts of Zhitomir and Lutsk (Volhynia); (2) Regions of Zhitomir and Tschutnov (Volhynia); (3) District of Emiltshino; (4) Regions of Radomyschl, Korostyshev, Olevsk and Ovrutsch; (5) Region of Zviahel; (6) General District of Dnepropetrovsk; (7) Krivoy Rog; (8) Chortitza; (9) Kronau; and (10) Korosten. In 79 villages there were lived 41,642 Jews (1941). There is a lack of data on people of other ethnic groups.
The death rate was **99.9%** (Jews and other ethnic-groups in West Ukraine). At about **0.12%** of people survived.
Other cases: Horodniza (3,784 Jews missing), Radomyschl (5,840 Jews missing), Slovetschno (5,591 Jews missing), Malin (8,745 Jews missing), *et cetera*.

Bessarabia

1941: Villages of Selz, Kandel, Bischofsfeld (Jeremovka), Hoffnungsfeld, Mannheim, Sebastiansfeld, Lichtenfeld, Worms, Landau, Rosenfeld, and Rastatt witnessed executions of children of mixed marriages but their German fathers or mothers.

19.08.1941: 3145 Jews were murdered in Zhytomyr's ghetto.

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR) (Russia) 1941

Reichskommissariat Ukraine
(Created 09.1941-09.1942)

District of Nazi Reich

Right Bank

Left Bank

Kiev

1943: Organization of Ukrainian Nationalists (Germanophile position) (Andriy Atansovich Mel'nyk) - Created in Volhynia-Podolia province.

150 Mel'nyk's partisans (core members)

...“with the help of the Nazi we [the legion] must destroy as many Bolsheviks as possible.”

Nazi-sponsored Ukrainian Legion of Self-Defense
Ukrains'kyi Legion Samooborony

Nazi military rule (09.1941-09.1942)

Jewish murder cases

Pro-Soviet partisan murder cases

05.-12.1942: 100 murders in Volhynia

10.1943: killings and displacement of the Poles in Volhynia

1941: Organization of Ukrainian Nationalists (Stepan Bandera)

Bessarabia

Transnistria

Members: (a) Ethnic Ukrainians (absolute majority of Legion personnel); but this diverse group included: (b) Volhynian Mel'nykites (members and sympathizers); (c) Petlyurists (officers of anti-Bolshevik (West) Ukrainian People's Republic; (d) Banderists; (e) Easterners (natives of pre-1939 Soviet Ukraine; and (f) few native Germany of Nazi party. The police forces were important instrument in implementation of Nazi program for Ukraine. It includes extermination of Jews.

Partisan movement

Volodymyr-Volyns'kyi

02.1944: Conflict with Polish and Soviet partisans

Reichskommissariat Ukraine
(09.1941-09.1942)****

District of Nazi Reich

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR)
(Russia) **1942**

22.06.1941 (4.00 A.M.): > 3000000 Nazi soldiers were committed armed attack against the territory of independent and sovereign State USSR, despite the Molotov-Ribbentrop pack of nonaggression (23.09.1939)

(fell on 19.09.1941)
Kiev

Soviet Army pushed Nazi out of Kiev on 06.11.1943

Left Bank

Right Bank, so-called Dnieper Ukraine

Ukraine borderline according to the adapted map.

Nazi military rule (09.1941-09.1942)

Lutsk (26.06.1941)

Rivne (29.06.1941)

Zhytomyr (08.07.1941)

15.07.1941:
Nazi/RSFSR hostilities

(The area achieved for 3 months)

Area: 340000 km²

01.09.1942

28.06.1942

26.09.1941

11.1942

Transcarpathia
(Subcarpathian Rus'). Until 1914 it belongs to Habsburg Empire.

Transnistria

Bessarabia

**** The map is adapted to: K. Berkhoff, Harvest of Despair: Life and Death in Ukraine under Nazi Rule, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 2004 [ISBN 0674013131].

Reichskommissariat Ukraine
(09.1941-09.1942)****

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR) (Russia) 1942

In total, area: **340000 km²**;
it was "prepared" for German settlement by killing non-Germans (Slavs and Jews) „immediately" (cited: p.44).

1942: 34000 Jews were murdered in Babi Yar

Nazi military rule (09.1941-09.1942)

In total, **350000** Jews were murdered within end-1942/1943 (p.69).

1941-1942: The Organization of Ukrainian Nationalists of Bandera and his ally Iaroslav Stetsko tried to set up an independent Ukraine state in Lviv (p.35^[1]).

1939: 1533000 Jews minority in Soviet Ukraine (< 5%).

22.06.1941: There were **20–25 mln** people in the territory of *Reichskommissariat Ukraine* at its shown greatest extent (01.09.1942.) (p.36)

01.01.1943: There were 16910008 inhabitants in the territory of *Reichskommissariat Ukraine* at its shown greatest extent (01.09.1942.) (p.37) or **≈ 25 %** of the people (or at about **3 mln only Slavs excluding from Russian prisoners**) were lost.

Transcarpathia (Subcarpathian Rus'). Until 1914 it belongs to Habsburg Empire.

Bessarabia

Transnistria

1941/1942: Bogdanovka massacre of 40000–50000 Jews by Nazi army, Ukrainian auxiliary forces, and Romanian gendarmes.

1944-1945 (in Bulgaria): There were 51000 Jewish survivors#.
1944-1945 (in Bulgaria and Romania): There were killed 12000 Jews###.

Victimization within 1944-1945 by Regions#

Region	Jews population	Victims [number]	Death rate [%]
Romania (The Regat)	221313	7000	3.2
Northern Bukovina	155313	141313	91.0
Southern Transylvania	41000	0	0.0
Transnistria	110000	110000	100.0
Bessarabia and Northern Bukovina	155313	141313	91.0
Southern Bukovina and Dorohoi	29687	27192	91.6
Bulgaria	51000	0	0.0
Thrace	4273	4075	95.4
Macedonia and Piroto	7581	7318	96.5
Dobruzha	700	0	0.0

[1] Chapter 2 "The Making of a Soviet Ukrainian City" in The Ukrainian West by W. Risch, Harvard Historical Studies Vol. 173, Harvard University Press (2011), pp. 1–347 [https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674061262].
**** The map is adapted to: K. Berkhoff, Harvest of Despair: Life and Death in Ukraine under Nazi Rule, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 2004 [ISBN 0674013131].
#E. Hollander, The final solution in Bulgaria and Romania: A comparative perspective. East European Politics and Societies 22 (2008) 207-247.
##P. Lobacev, Kad se Volga ulivala u Savu. Moj zivotni roman, Belgrade, Prosveta (1997) 124.

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR) (Russia) 1941

Reichskommissariat Ukraine
(Created **09.1941-09.1942**)

Nazi military rule
(09.1941-09.1942)

District of Nazi Reich

Right Bank

Left Bank

Kiev

1941-1944: Romanian authorities had established **200 Jewish ghettos and labor camps in Transnistria.**

1941: Ion Antonescu envisioned "purification" of Romania of all ethnic minorities (30 % after I WW), due to policy of ethnic intolerance, antisemitism, and process of "Romanization" of the nation. The ethnic cleansing in Romania includes Jewish, Ukrainians, Bulgarians, Russians, Gagauz, and Roma.

07.1941: According to Nazi-Romanian convention 93500 ethnic Germans were "repatriated" from Bessarabia. The Soviet authorities had deported 17000-22000 multi-ethnic people from Bessarabia to the East just before the German-Romanian attack. „The deported to eastern parts of the Soviet Union in 1941 had a much greater chance of surviving than the "lucky" ones who were "spared" deportation". Two days after the attack there was established *Reichskommissariat Ukraine*.

Transnistria
05.1944: 3000 Jewish were saved by the Red Army

Zhmerinka Ghetto
(Vinitsa region)

Transnistria

1939: 114000 Bulgarians were "exchanged" from Ukraine to Bulgaria† (p. 147).

Romania

Bessarabia
06.1940: 49818 km² and 3700000 inhabitants (incl. Northern Bukovina)

Bessarabia

1941-03.1943: In Bessarabia, Bukovina, and the Danube delta there were displaced 1300000 ethnic Bulgarians, Ukrainians, and Russians. The Romanians did not solicit the opinion of neither Ukraine nor Soviet Union for the population exchange, It was violation of the international law,

07.09.1940: At about 60000 ethnic Bulgarians were "exchanged" from Northern Dobrudja to Bulgaria.

†W. Kolarz, Russia and her colonies. George Philip and Son Ltd. (1952),London.

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR)
(Russia) **1942-1948**

1943: The Ukrainian Insurgent Army of Taras Bulba-Borovets killed ca. 40000–60000 of Volhynia's 200 000 Poles (p.35^[1]).

1941-1945: Ukrainian nationalist groups had killed up to 20000-25000 of Eastern Galicia's Poles (p.35^[1]).

1945-1948: Ukrainian Insurgent Army of Taras Bulba-Borovets waged particularly fierce guerrilla warfare against the RSFSR and Poles (p.36^[1]).

02.1944-25.05.1946: 110825 members of Ukrainian nationalistsArmy ad bands were killed by Soviet forces (p.36^[1]).

[1] Chapter 2 "The Making of a Soviet Ukrainian Cit" in The Ukrainian West by W. Risch, Harvard Historical Studies Vol. 173, Harvard University Press (2011), pp. 1–347 [https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674061262].

Territorial expansion of Ukraine 1915-1954

1945-1991

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR) (Russia)

Interdependence of the former Soviet Union's republics was greater than in any other federal or multinational state worldwide (p. 134[†]).

19.02.1954: Presidium Supreme Council's decision of linking administratively Crimea province to Ukraine SSR. Before, this date Crimea were not included in any project of Ukraine nation.
26.04.1954: Transfer of Crimea to Ukraine SSR.

Table: Polygon area values of shown Ukraine provinces A1-A8.

Year	Province	Polygon area
1915	A2	3.8350
	A3	3.7891
	A4	4.0329
	A5	6.0224
1918	A6	4.5862
	A7	3.2966
1945	A1	119593.87
1954	A8	4.4498

In order to assess a legitimacy of claim for victim State-Russia, perhaps, there can go on to argue that within 1915-1954 State-Ukraine show dramatic territorial expansion (figure) mainly from Russia and in wartime of State-Russia as well as when there is changing of socio-political system of State-Russia (1961). When State-Russia are involved into armed conflicts or there is destabilized, respectively, changed their socio-political system, then, the events are always associated with territorial expansion of State-Ukraine; or, the Ukraine-State are interested in Russia's involving in armed conflicts.

[†]G. Mirsky, Chapter 7: Ukraine, In On Ruins of Empire: Ethnicity and Nationalism in the Former Soviet Union. Westport, CT: Praeger (1997) Contributions in Political Science. Bloomsbury Collect. [ISBN: 978-0-313-30044-8].

1922-1991

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR) (Russia)

Land property 1922-1991

19.02.1918: *Socialisation of Land:* The State (RSFSR) is the only possible owner of land.

12.12.1919: Criminal Code.

22.05.1922: Basic Civil Rights.

Decree determined property in land dating **06.1922:** The private property in land is under certain limits, determined within Provision 1[‡].

(1)...*The right of property in buildings in towns and rural districts which are not municipalized by local soviets up to the date of publication of this decree...*

(The right to transfer a lease does not cover plots of land in rural districts.)

(2) „*Terms of agreement with local authorities managing land and the right of buildings thereupon in town or rural districts within a fixed period of the law, not to exceed forty-nine years*“...

Treaty of establishment of RSFSR (**30.12.1922**): RSFSR (USSR; Soviet Russia) had/have been socio-political system: Soft-federation of SSRs, including State called „Ukraine SSR**“, who are dissolved by Belavezha Accords (08.12.1991).

Jurisprudense between the sharp change of the two socio-political systems (Russian Empire and Soviet Russia)

Old Empire lawyers were allowed to work and publish in Law Review: Law and Life, 1922-1931.

New Soviet Russia lawyers publish in Law Review: Soviet Law, 1922.

Republic	Date of formation or entrance into the Soviet Union
1917	
RSFSR	07.11.1917
1922	
Ukrainian SSR	30.12.1922
Belorussian SSR	30.12.1922
1924	
Turkmen SSR	17.10.1924
Uzbek SSR	27.10.1924
1929	
Tadzhik SSR	05.12.1929
1936	
Kazakh SSR	05.12.1936
Georgian SSR	05.12.1936
Azerbaijan SSR	05.12.1936
Kirghiz SSR	05.12.1936
Armenian SSR	05.12.1936
1940	
Moldavian SSR	02.08.1940
Lithuanian SSR	03.08.1940
Latvian SSR	05.08.1940
Estonian SSR	06.08.1940

26.04.1954: Soviet Russia administratively have linked Crimea province to Ukraine SSR.

Ukraine SSR: Legislative territory within **30.12.1922-08.12.1991.**

[‡]“Official language” denotes the language of the State’s administration.

**On 30.12.1922, the borderline of State called Ukraine SSR excludes from Crimea.

1945-1991

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR) (Russia)

1954-1958: Khrushchev gave significant authority to Republics' Agencies in economic and Judicial matters.

Year	Ukrainians [%]	Russians [%]	Others [%]
1944	26.4	5.5	68.1
1951	42.8	30.8	26.4
1955	44.2	35.6	20.2
1959	60.16	27.06	12.78
1979	74.0	19.3	6.7
1989	79.13	16.07	4.8

Population of Lviv within 1944-1987 (p.42^[2]).

*Under „Others“ there is understood mainly Poles.

1931:16.3% Ukrainians (p.31^[2]).

1944:62.8% Poles (p.34^[2]).

01.01.1945:2.3% Poles (8600 people) (p.34^[2]).
Due to street violence (12.1944) provoked by Ukrainian nationalists and the NKVD there were arrests and exile of Poles; forced Ukrainization; and, bilingualism (Ukrainian and Russian languages.)

1980s: Lviv became the scene of first mass protests against policies in Soviet Ukraine. The turn to an explicitly anti-Soviet people's identity dates since 1985. Although, it is difficult to claim for that 'Soviet nation' was/has been successfully created.

10.12.1956: 45000 Ukrainian nationalist guerrillas and their allies had returned to Western Ukraine; almost, 41000 to the countryside.

1961: 26th Party Congress: Process of de-Stalinization**.

RSFSR Constitution (1977):
Article 72: Each Soviet Republic has rights to withdraw USSR;
Article 76: Republics are Sovereign;
Article 80: The Soviet Republics have rights into relations with foreign States.

15.08.1944: Plane for establishing Ukrainian language, cultural and educational institutions; use of the Ukrainian language in Party and State (Ukraine SSR) institutions.

12.06.1953: Due to larger campaign against "Great Russian chauvinism" by the Communist Party of the Soviet Union there was promoted local nationals to positions of leadership, particularly highlighting Ukraine SSR, the Baltic Republics, and Belarus (p. 20^[1]).
The policy by Lavrenty Beria has promoted ethnic Ukrainian as Republic's second Party secretary in addition to co-opting the outlawed during that time Ukrainian Uniate Church. Nationalists and their supporters including members of Western Ukraine's Uniate Church clergy were returned from labor camps and places of exile.

Since 1953: The Communist Party of the Soviet Union's policy favored collective forms of leadership, the end of mass repression, greater focus on individual forms of self-expression, materialist values, and much rights for non-Russian ethnics. The RSFSR did not aim to nurture traditional Russian values; rather, they fostered de-ethnicisation of Russians and the ethnicisation of non-Russians^[3].

20th Party Congress (1956): Khrushchev had promoted policy of restoring norms of democracy and establishing relations between policy elite and the society in addition to reveal the crimes committed by Stalin's cult of personality. This had included illegal repression of Party and State leaders in the late 1930s. The Congress emphasized the need to develop non-Russians cultures.

** Stalinism: A general line of ruling party policy within 1927 (15th Party Congress) and 1961 (26th Party Congress) (34 years).
[1] Chapter 1 'Lviv and Postwar Soviet Politics' in The Ukrainian West by W. Risch, Harvard Historical Studies Vol. 173, Harvard University Press (2011), pp. 1-347 [https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674061262].
[2] Chapter 2 'The Making of a Soviet Ukrainian City' in The Ukrainian West by W. Risch, Harvard Historical Studies Vol. 173, Harvard University Press (2011), pp. 1-347 [https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674061262].
[3] A. Wierzbicki, Ethnicity and Power in the Soviet Union. Post-Soviet Issues. 4 (2017) 240-255 [DOI: 10.24975/2313-8920-2017-4-3-240-255].

1988-1992

Russian Soviet Federative Socialist Republic (RSFSR/USSR)
(Russia)

Lviv

17.03.1991 (Referendum)

Question: "Do you consider necessary the preservation of the RSFSR as a renewed federation of equal and sovereign republics, in which the rights and freedoms of an individual of any nationality will be fully guaranteed?"

76.4 % voted „yes“

The Republics, Lithuania, Armenia, Latvia, Estonia, Georgia, and Moldova boycotted the Referendum. **Ukraine did not do so.**

RSFSR Treaty by Gorbachev since **03.12.1990/17.12.1990.**

06.1991. Yeltsin's election as President of RSFSR (with majority votes).

Novo-Ogarevo Treaty (Draft of RSFSR Treaty by Gorbachev according to the Referendum's results from 17.03.1991) (**20.08.1991.**)

25.12.1991. Gorbachev has resumed his position as President of RSFSR (He has been elected only by the lower House of the Parliament).

18.08.1992. Gorbachev has resumed his position as President of RSFSR.

Other SSRs

***Stalinism*: A general line of ruling party policy within 1927 (15th Party Congress) and 1961 (26th Party Congress) (34 years).

[1] Chapter 1 'Lviv and Postwar Soviet Politics' in The Ukrainian West by W. Risch, Harvard Historical Studies Vol. 173, Harvard University Press (2011), pp. 1-347 [https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674061262].

[2] Chapter 2 'The Making of a Soviet Ukrainian Cit' in The Ukrainian West by W. Risch, Harvard Historical Studies Vol. 173, Harvard University Press (2011), pp. 1-347 [https://doi.org/10.4159/harvard.9780674061262].

Author's note (2)

There is much more to be said; and, it should be said, about the discussed period 1945–1991 of development of RSFSR and their SSRs; thus, tracking connection among past and current events of the history of Eastern Europe as an effort to provide further arguments for effect of past events on the Ukraine-Russia conflict since 2014. Many of these events, however, are/have been contradictory interpreted by many policy elites of post-RSFS-Republics, including Ukrainian' one.

To begin with, looking at Mr. Meri's words, regarding, the discussed period 1940–1991 of development of, for instance, State Estonia*, there has been highlighted '...the fifty years of exclusion from Europe...' (p. 1016^[1]), and "...The totalitarian Soviet regime had been honed to perfection. Rather than the economy, in control of the people's ability to think, their creativity. The upper limit of creativity was determined by the low level of intellectual power wielded by the most tragic consequence of this was the true and final liberation of the people heaviest burden—the obligation to think, to make independent decisions responsible for themselves". He also mention the "points out the responsibility of the Western the loss of Estonia's independence". The narrative follows the logic NATO and highlights the 'Soviet incompetence', as well.

In the light of the major aim of the current contribution, there are highlighted only those interpretations which contradict with (arti)facts about the history of Russia such as the aforementioned ones, because of not only Central and Eastern Europe, but also West Europe have occupied a significant position in developing nationalism as philosophy and studies; thus, concentrating on formation of a considerable number of new nation-states after IWW in place of the former European empires shown above. Despite, the fact that the result of which as the events from Ukraine-Russia conflicts show did not lead to a stable European and international order. Thus, to discuss about loss of independence of State by the highlighted region of Europe contradicts with the fact that the nationalism, first is regarded as a typical modern phenomenon dating since, at the beginning of 20th CE.

It is, particularly wrong to state that after the 1990s when the RSFSR are dissolved there are new nation-states who again proliferated^[2], because of within the RSFSR there were/are at about 100 nationalities in context ethnics who completely have preserved their histories, languages, cultures, and religious traditions, particularly underlying the policy since 1953 to a level that many scholars claim for almost complete loosened control by the central power on the domestic SSRs policy elites in 1989^[3]. As an effort to secure the cooperation with the Baltics States on the so-called *perestroika* Gorbachev legalized, for instance the Popular Front of Estonia (1988) who are movement of nationalists. Therefore, since 1953 the SSRs were/are effectively independent Republics and the policy is described as democratic and liberal — it is often called *liberal nationalism* — in addition to the fact that the dissolution of the Soviet Union was not only inevitable, but also it was unexpected for many policy elites including in many West States classifying the socio-policy system during that time in RSFSR as a stable#-one. The remarkable lack of accurate prognoses by Western scholars is highlighted^[4]. Still, in 1917 the establishment of RSFSR (07.11.1917) was as Union of sovereign national Republics, where 'self-determination' from standpoint of history and economy is determined within the as political context, and state autonomy; thus, making a national state^[4]. The socio-policy system of RSFSR is classified as highly bureaucratic[‡] system, but not lacking of democracy one. As major destabilizing factors of the Soviet Union are highlighted (i) the unsuccessful conflict in Afghanistan (1988-1989) — Afghanistan are the major targets of the recent RSFSR economic offensive in underdeveloped countries worldwide until 1980s, while their fast economic development until 1950s was due to the United States of America and the United Nations assistances. —, (ii) the expenses due to Chernobyl (Ukraine) act (1986), and (iii) the earthquake that devastated Armenia (1988). Events (i)–(iii) and the fact that policy elites of namely Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania took significant control over their SSRs have promoted many anti-Russian protests, therein^[5]. As a key factor affecting the dissolution of the Soviet Union is activity of the aforementioned Popular Front of Estonia who became popular in other SSRs, including Ukraine and Belarus. Their organized protests against environmentally dangerous industries of RSFSR reflecting in mind Chernobyl act, however, without to account for the fact that it is in the territory of independent Ukraine SSR are the nutshell events of dissolution of the Union, because of they induce a year latter pro-reformer movements in other SSRs, particularly, highlighting the Slavic Republics and the seven Caucasus' SSRs. During 1980s environmental concerns were regarded as notable catalyst of social mobilization in Russia and most SSRs^[6]. In Kazakhstan, for instance, the environmental movement during the latter period has mostly international character^[7].

Conversely, in other SSRs these movements was nationalist ones. The environmental issue concerning mainly effects of pollution and radioactive contamination was voiced by the novel national groups of SSRs, particularly highlighting the National Fronts including the Russian nationalists in the RSFSR. The environmental issue was/has been/is significantly important in Russia, due to environmental deprecation. Owing to the fact that both the RSFSR and their successors present-day Russian Federation are the largest country on Earth, but only 23.8%^[8] of the territory has certain and favourable economic and administrative characteristics, due to temperate rain forest biome type. The remaining 76.2% show chiefly polar desert one, and in fact, represent almost untouched natural expanses. At about 55% of Russia's land has not been affected by human activity^[9]. The environmental problems and policies had/were/have global consequences for the climat change. Due to these reasons, the Society's activism on environmental issues was/is highlighted in RSFSR and in present-day Russia, despite variety of political conditions. The spatially restricted highly industrialized areas caused for the fact that the three of the of the world's ten dirtiest cities worldwide are in Russia (2006)^[10] and an agreement that the rapid industrialization within 1920–1953 had degraded significantly the environment of these highly industrialized areas. The environmental issue, therefore, in RSFSR and present-dat Russia was/is most urgent.

A mix of factors has shaped the policy decisions within 1985–1991. A factor matters significantly when the issue is enough prominent; attracts public attention; and, media. How party leaders of SSRs have instrumentalized the environmental issue and Chernobyl act (1986) as an attempt to further destabilize the socio-policy system of Russia during Gorbachev's administration?

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[3] U.S.S.R. AND EASTERN EUROPE: END OF AN ERA? Foreign Policy Association, *Great Decisions* (1990) pp. 5-16.

[4] A. Wierzbicki, Ethnicity and Power in the Soviet Union. *Post-Soviet Issues*. 4 (2017) 240–255 [DOI: 10.24975/2313-8920-2017-4-3-240-255].

[5] D. Marples, Revisiting the Collapse of the USSR. *Canadian Slavonic Papers/Revue Canadienne des Slavistes*. 53 (2011) 461-473.

[6] Dawson, *Eco-Nationalism*; Yanitskii, *Ekologicheskoe dvizhenie Rossii*; and Babcock, "gRole of Public Interest Groups".

[7] Shatz, "Notes on 'the Dog That Didn't Bark.'"

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*State Estonia is member-State of RSFSR since 06.08.1940.

**Lennart Meri was born in 1929 into the family of an Estonian diplomat. Due to father's profession, Meri spent a large part of his childhood abroad, attending primary school in both Berlin and Paris. The Meri family was deported 1941 (there were killed, deported, or disappeared under mysterious circumstances at about 60000 ethnic estonians within 1940-1941). Meri's father was sent to a concentration camp and his mother, with her two sons, was exiled to Siberia. In 1945, the family returned to Estonia in 1953 Meri graduated from the University of Tartu as a historian and ethnographer. He was elected President of Estonia in 1992 by the Riigikogu and served two terms in office (1992-1996 and 1996-2001).

†The term „stable” in the context of socio-policy system refers mainly to a system lacking of „violence” and „structural changes”; and, having „governmental longevity/duration,” and „legitimate constitutional regime,” respectively.

‡The term refers to structure institutions and decision making processes in an offices hierarchy.

In relation to purpose of author's note (2) and this contribution it should be noted that the issue of environmental protection in RSFSR was/has been tackled within the 15 ministries responsible for a particular sector of economy^[1].

Notably, there had/has/have a completely adequate legislature, regarding environmental concerns in RSFSR (Russia); thus, allowing for authorities' enacting regulations restricting chemicals, including radioactive pollutants, because of Soviet Russia had/have disposed at about 2.5 million curies of radioactive waste since 1965, restricted by the law. If authorities have failed to meet requirements within 1953-1986, perhaps, the problem could be found in relatively restricted numbers of separate state authorities. Perhaps, due to these reasons in 1988 there has been established further State Committee on Environmental Protection (*Goskompriroda*^{*}).

It is broadly acknowledged that in spite of the fact that there were since 1957 a large number of party and governmental resolutions in addition to those ones, since 1917, together with numerous legal enactments and the strictness, regarding environmental standards, there were rather ineffective mechanisms of their enforcement within the territories of SSRs.

The *Goskompriroda* have conducted environmental reviews for novel projects within the Russia, however, within 1985-1991 there is monopoly of single party to many SSRs; thus, lacking debates on environmental issues.

The environmental protection gained stature following the establishment of the Russian Federation, as well. The Federal Act on Protection of Natural Environment (1991) is among the first laws passed by the Russian Federation^[2]. There are also developed a set of special laws in many particular spheres of environmental protection.

Since, the major author's point is not to study neither Soviet Union's administrative structures nor to tackle environmental issue of RSFSR or the present-day Russian Federation, but to detail on how the Chernobyl act in Ukraine (1986) has been instrumentalised to political purposes by party leaders of SSRs, particularly highlighting environmental protests organized by National fronts including of Estonia, among others, I shall look mainly at how affect the Chernobyl act (1986) on the Gorbachev's administration and how Ukraine SSR have lacked responsibility neither for the act nor for the victims. The victimology, due to the discussed act is not acknowledged by the policy elite of present-day Ukraine, as well.

The coincidence of Chernobyl act and its affect on the environment of Russia, of course including Ukraine and Belarus, opened up public debates on environmental protection and state's responsibility^[3]. Thus, the Gorbachev's administration are faced with, as is acknowledged, first large popular protests against administration and RSFSR's authorities^[4].

Owing to that the Chernobyl act has been committed in the territory of independent Ukraine SSR it has been significant challenge of developing effective laws; thus, ensuring, on the one hand effective environmental protection, and on the other hand, effective legal pursuing of States responsibility.

At this point it is instructive to note the remark on „*poorly functioning legal systems*“ which is frequently used to study socio-polycy administration of RSFSR^[5] and the actual rather lack of effectiveness of the legal system of Russia within the territory of SSRs. Due to these circumstances during 1985-1989 the author comes to view that the Chernobyl act has been the major motivation behind the Gorbachev's legal reform. In order the author's hypothesis to contribute to advancing further in-depth understanding of circumstances during that time, it must be testable. This means that there should be observable implications.

Perhaps, it could be evaluated to be consistent with evidence that the *Goskompriroda* has been established in 1988 — two years after the Chernobyl act. Due to aforementioned a lack of debate with monopoly party leaders of SSRs *Goskompriroda* have been ineffective on territory outside Russia.

The hypotheses are rejected frequently more decisively than they are accepted. Any hypotheses more or less implies observable evidences and evidence can be found, due to coincidence even if it is wrong. Thus, there remains to apply strong scientific practice justifying scientific knowledge. In the latter context, there should be consensus providing a basis for relying on the true of claims and hypotheses, despite, a strong scientific consensus could be also wrong which could allow us to overturn accepted understandings regarding “*totalitarian character*“ of RSFSR's socio-polycy system within 1945-1991; or “*a lack of competence*“; “*a lack of pure legal system*“; “*a lack of independence*“ of SSRs, *et cetera*, and *et cetera*. As the author has attempted to sketch such as consensus does not exists currently, and might not exist not only due to a huge number of uncertainty of statements and controversial claims by authors discussing, debating or disputing events and circumstances during that time, but also because of key question lies far beyond the available knowledge of the Chernobyl act and the state responsibility of Ukraine, respectively, Ukraine SSR.

Furthermore, there is a low scientific interest; the evidences, so far, are not fully resolved; or if they are resolved, then they are not still publicly available; also, the issue has importance to policy. It is also connected with Ukraine-Russia conflict 2014-(2024). There is demanding by policy-making processes, as well.

Despite the fact that political elites are concerned not with what is true, but with what there should be done according to collective action of society the administration is connected with argumentations and decisions adopted by government institutions. In the case of Ukraine-Russia conflict 2014-(2024) it should be accounted for that the Chernobyl act committed in the territory of independent Ukraine SSR not only appears one of the major factors, but even it is the most important one. It crucially destabilises the socio-political system of RSFSR and affects dramatically the Russia's environment and the health of generations of Russians; and, not only, of course.

However, the purpose of this contribution is events/acts/crimes detailing on victimology of ethnic Russians and State Russia due to policy by administration of both the Ukraine SSR and present-day Ukraine. Due to these reasons, the issue of the Chernobyl act (1986) is tackled, herein, from the perspective of victimology of Russians and Russia.

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My point of view, herein, is that, there is needed to all information about events, which should be epistemically convenient, because of the science is collective knowledge of environmental — in a broad context — phenomena. The classified (unpublished) data on Chernobyl act prevent us from an in-depth causal analysis. There are claims that specialised data are inaccurate^[1]. Despite, first, Chernobyl reactors' type was not used in West^[2]. However, RSFSR-Bulgaria relations in the field of nuclear energy rooted in 1945. Within 1945–1991 there were/are utilised only RSFSR made nuclear power plant technologies in Bulgaria without accidents/acts^[3].

Nevertheless, narrative referring to anti-East European/anti-Soviet technologies or human stereotypes can be found in West media; implying that plant staff were less skilled and reactors less well designed in East than in West^[2]. Such texts are excluded from the author's analysis. Toward Chernobyl' act's health impact in Eastern Europe, the narrative was apocalyptic^[2]. Unfortunately, recently it can be also found texts like: "...*legacy of the totalitarian societies in Eastern Europe is catastrophic...*" or "*in 50 years they have destroyed irreplaceable resources and created untold sources of pollution that will threaten the planet for centuries*"...^[4].

There is a lack of objective arguments (see below) for such writings. Minimum, the environmental assessment of pollution has been performed by both domestic and international authorities. However, I should note that the International Atomic Energy Agency have recognised the need for international radioactive waste management programs in...1989^[4]; thus, lacking to seek neither to provide con-arguments against highly politicised anti-East European/anti-Soviet statements^[4] nor to discuss motivation behind them, because of it is known.

Rather, the author wants to know causal relations among movements of nationalists in SSRs after the Chernobyl act and their destabilising affect on Gorbachev's administration. There are national movements not only in Russia, but also in Belarus, Ukraine, Latvia and Lithuania, respectively. An anti-nuclear movement emerged in Kazakhstan, as well^[5]. The movement secured powerful politician (Mr. Nazarbayev) who further led (1989) Kazakhstan to independence and ruled ca. 30 years, the Republic until his resignation in 2019; Kazakhstan's nuclear arsenal — the world's fourth largest one. Present-day Kazakhstan is global leader in nuclear non-proliferation.

Despite, let us review some of available facts which we would need to know in order to argue my statements.

The power plant's reactor 4 (Chernobyl) exploded, due to "a routine safety test"; thus, scattering radiation and killing at least 31 people immediately^[5,6]; 80 people died immediately and ca. 2000 people died on the way to hospitals^[7]; 28 people died immediately^[8].

The act has been reflected not only in Ukraine SSR, but also in all SSRs; West European States; the United States of America, and Bulgaria^[3], among others, with heavily politicised actions. Randomised publications provide us with a tool to assess affect on policy-making processes of SSRs, despite, controversy, regarding date, time, number of victims, *et cetera, et cetera*.

Thus, there is shown 25.04.1986 (23.23h), 25.04.1986 (23.10h), 25.04.1986 (21.23h) or locally 26.04.1986 (1.23h)^[7,9]. At about 10-15% of volatile radionuclides escaped from the reactor into the atmosphere; ca. 3% of other radionuclides; and 100% of the noble gases (p.79^[10]).

Toward, scattered radiation, immediately, after news the UK Foreign and Commonwealth Office asked the National Radiological Protection Board to tackle radiological implications showing external γ -ray doses in Moscow $0.2 \mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and in Bulgaria $0.7 \mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ (p.72^[11] according to domestic authorities; UK ones show $0.3 \mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) (see Table 1^[9], as well.)

For Belarus, reports show $2.0 \mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ ^[8] or ca. ten times higher*. In Chernobyl were measured $150 \mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ ^[11]. Perhaps, it is an average value, because of 24000 people living within 3–15 km from the plant were received within $350\text{--}550 \mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ average doses^[8]. The area outside the *evacuation zone* was shown comparable doses with external natural radiation^[8]. The increased values of γ -ray doses in Bulgaria assumes that the winds are blowing westwards. There has been published that the winds in Russia are blowing eastwards, not westwards^[2].

Despite winds' direction the International Atomic Energy Agency were concluded that there are released due to Chernobyl act more than 100 radioactive elements into the environment with greatest concentrations in Russia, Belarus, and Ukraine^[6,12], who are the most severe contaminated countries. There were lesser concentrations within Scandinavia and South-Central Europe^[6]. The complete list of radionuclide emissions of reactor 4 as reported to International Atomic Energy Agency can be found (Table 2^[9]). According to^[13] radioactive pollutants affected Ukraine, Belarus, and Russia, but also Scandinavian countries, Central and Eastern Europe. According to^[14] there were measured ^{131}I $10\text{--}2.5 \text{ Bq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ (29.04.1986), which is inconvenienced with regard to public health. The isotopes ^{131}I , ^{90}Sr and ^{137}Cs were sources of radiation exposure^[8,15] causing for both the external radiation and ingestion of polluted food.

For purpose of this contribution, I should remark on that even this information not exact it is sufficient to settle causality, regarding Chernobyl act and policy making decisions in SSRs. Despite, uncertainty of death rates of Chernobyl's radioactive fallout, predictive models show that within 3000-30000 people will die of cancer as a result of the act; thus, highlighting the most affected States, *i.e.* Russian, Belarus, and Ukraine, because of the low-level radiation may be far more dangerous^[16]. Depending on model, there are deduced even up to 500000 cancer and leukemia deaths worldwide^[16]. The act left at about 27 nearby cities and villages contaminated for people to live, therein, and 135000 people were evacuated^[16]; 350000 evacuated^[2]; 100000 evacuated^[8]. Three years after the act more than 20 cities in RSFSR are being evacuated, as well as, despite, reports by Western health physicists, showing a lack of detectable health problems^[12], due to significant amount of spent subsidy by Russia on clean-up of territories of Russia, Belarus, and Ukraine. Report by UN World Health Organization (1989) confirmed that the territories of SSRs was under control; thus, lacking detectable health problems for citizens. There was additional case-control test by the Atomic Energy Commission, regarding cancers, disease, birth defects of citizens of the regions, however, the protocol was not peer reviewed^[2,12]. Only childhood thyroid cancer was shown as possible affect.

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*The natural background doses vary within $0.1\text{--}0.2 \mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$.

In April 2020 there is increasing in radiation levels around Chernobyl; thus, again releasing radioactive material stored in the environment^[1] (see also^[2], among others.) It is impossible to determine direct causality between Chernobyl act as a major factor affecting on policy decisions of SSRs; thus, destabilizing the RSFSR (1989). We are able to establish correlation among events and facts and to seek for Ukraine (including Ukraine SSR) State's responsibility, however. It is easy to see that there is significant amount of spent subsidy by Russia for environmental cleaning of Ukraine, Russia, and Belarus, due to Chernobyl act; also, involved large-scale operators (up to 600000 people) within 1986–1988 by military servants of Russia^[3]. Many of Russian armed forces who were active in Chernobyl clean-up tasks became ill^[3]. Importantly, there should be highlighted the failing to include costs and expenses of nuclear waste storage in economic analysis which was again covered by Russia, despite, many nuclear power plants within 1945-1991 were and still are located in the territory of Ukraine SSR and present day Ukraine. Further: A particular author's remark on is that in the Eastern European countries, including Bulgaria, among others until 1991 are no developed coordinated programs for radioactive waste management^[4], while the need from such programs for the latter purposes as we have already seen has been recognized by International Atomic Energy Agency in 1989. The most obvious persons who should probably bear highest health and financial risks and effects due to Chernobyl act and nuclear waste storage are next generations primary Russians (of course, Belarussians and Ukrainians, as well as,) despite, the Chernobyl act has been committed on the territory of Ukraine SSR and there was/is a lack of self-responsibility of neither the Ukrainian government in SSR nor the present-day one. There is rogue diplomacy of Ukraine SSR (including Belarus SSR) during 1986-1989 which is real problem for the Gorbachev's administration^[5]. Apart from doubt regarding *accidence* of the Chernobyl act or a (single) *team operators' error*, there is a complete lack of adequacy of Ukrainian SSR Security Services, both military and civil ones who are primary responsible for events happened and acts committed in their territory. There is documented a lack of adequacy of emergency management and civil defense services of Ukraine SSR^[6]. The major citizens' concerns are regarding slow evacuation of victims of affected regions^[6]; also, a major criticism, regarding constructed hierarchy of risk for nuclear accidents by party leaders of Ukraine SSR (1982) where economic losses due to repair shutdowns of nuclear power plants are of primary importance comparing with health risks for population and environmental pollution. This is explicitly highlighted by the Ukrainian Ministry of Energy and Electrification^[6]. Yet, in the context of the purpose this contribution, *i.e.* assessing victimology of ethnic Russians and State Russia examining more carefully the discussed issue even without as is highlighted^[7] objective definitions of the so-called *environmental victimology* based mainly on subjective even self-definitions it is easy to see that again victims have been and are ethnic Russians (including Belarussians and Ukrainians); and, again major perpetrator is Ukraine (SSR). Despite, how we apply or use the legal term *victim* or how exactly it is defined from the perspective of environmental justice the present-day Ukrainian policy elite or Ukraine SSR party leaders do not and did not argue or identified victims of Chernobyl act or further health effects, due to the act neither among past nor from current or next generations Russians, Belarussians, and Ukrainians. A particular remark is on that the children are unable to identify themselves as victims, but they are. (Definitions of *environmental victims* can be viewed, herein^[7].) Turning back to past events dating since 1986, on the one hand, there is claims for independence of SSRs, highlighting explicitly Ukraine, among others, and seeking of party leader positions by domestic political leaders. On the other hand, the responsibility and costs due to Chernobyl act have been/are directed to Russia and high-level civilian Government Commission (Shcherbina) during that time^[8]. There is a lack of self-responsibility of policy elite of Ukrainian SSR. The Deputy Chairman of RSFSR has been addressed as primary responsible for organising post-accident administrative response. The facts are that in Chernobyl on 26.04.1986 (4.00 p.m.) or *ca.* 5h after the act there arrived the first team of nuclear specialists...from Moscow^[8] (696.57 km distance); thus, underlying, as aforementioned, a complete lack of adequacy of Ukrainian SSR government. At about one hour earlier the Kiev Military District have received an alert (3.12h, 26.04.1986), however, Colonel-General Pikalov of Chemical Troops was in the Carpathian Military District^[8]. The inadequate training and questionable policy Pikalov's decisions were highlighted^[8]. Lieutenant-Colonel Kushnin of Chemical Troops of the Kiev Military District did not arrive in Prypiat until 27.04^[8]. Further: It is documented that troops of RSFSR armed forces have performed internal missions in peacetime within the SSRs mainly providing emergency services, but not due to obligate. The mobilisation of thousands of active-duty RSFSR troops and reservists due to Chernobyl act has been underlined as unusual occurrence regarding number and variety of military units, scope, and duration of intervention^[8]. Gorbachev's administration addressed the nation 11 days about the Chernobyl act^[9]. At this point there are posed question about adequacy of information within the policy elite of RSFSR, as well. The government documents on Chernobyl act are declassified in 1994 due to trial of RSFSR party^[9]. There is not needed a much more precise knowledge of facts regarding the Chernobyl act, but rather a manner of objective relating these facts showing that for act having dramatically negative health and environmental effect on Russians and Belarussians as well as Russia, respectively Belarus, amongst others, of course, also regarded as a disaster of global proportions changing politics of nuclear power not only in RSFSR but also abroad, which happened/committed in territory of independent Ukraine SSR the primary responsibility, however, was looked at Russians in addition to enormous expenses again covered by Russia.

For the sake of argument, let us look at the next highlighted destabilizing factor of the Gorbachev's administration mentioned above, *i.e.* Armenian earthquake (07.12.1988). There could be considered a similar detail on^[8] RSFSR armed forces were called upon to respond to non-military crisis due to earthquake in Armenia. There are Civil Defence and Military Medical Services, Engineering Troops and Air Force; also, troops of Ministry of Interior liquidating consequences of the Armenian disaster.

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- [5] K. Brown, The big secret in the academy is that most research is secret. *The Politics of Knowledge* *Academe* 106 (2020) 15–21.
- [6] E. Geist, Political fallout: The failure of emergency management at Chernobyl'. *Slavic Review*. 74 (2015) 104–126.
- [7] C. Williams, An Environmental Victimology. *Social Justice*. 23 (1996) 16–40.
- [8] W. Potter, L. Kerne, The Soviet military's performance at Chernobyl. *Soviet Studies*. 43 (1991) 1027–1047.
- [9] J. Lillis, Kazakhstan's nuclear nightmare. *History Today* (August, 2019) 88–91 [https://www.historytoday.com/archive/behind-times/kazakhstan-nuclear-nightmare].

Turning back to policy-making decisions in RSFSR: On 16.11.1988 (the date of dissolution of the Soviet Union is 08.12.1991) the legislature of the Estonian SSR adopted changes in their Republic's constitution as still completely independent SSR of RSFSR, which reserved for Estonia the right to veto all Soviet Union legislation. A remark on the latter context is the notion of *independence* reflecting actual autonomy of a State, own language, justice, culture, internal affairs, agriculture, *et cetera*.

On 03.12.1990 when the Gorbachev's novel draft of the RSFSR Treaty has been approved by the Upper House of the RSFSR Parliament there were Estonian delegates, who again have organized anti-Russian protest. There is a lack of Latvia's delegates.

I would like also to stress that the first large-scale collective students' protests after 1985 in Kazakhstan were due to Gorbachev's request to replace the longtime ethnic Kazakh party leader^[4,5].

Despite, this limited form of representation of past events and, in fact, very restricted in its subject issue, one could clearly distinguish between political statements and historical facts of the policy movements of Russia and Estonia, among others SSRs from the near-past of the States. The latter facts are highlighted as an effort to emphasize how mimetic remains the representation of socio-political systems of SSRs talking about their independence from the central power within the RSFSR. Mimetic skills of policy elites of post-SSRs represents a novel level of development of culture of these post-SSRs Societies involving of a collective anti-Russian model of society, which is used as can be expected to coordination of corresponding society and, respectively, their social control.

However, once when we have such statements as the shown above ones, in order to determine their justification we must answer a lot of questions. There is needed to know, for instance, what state a policy elite of the State must be in the discussed period, because of the Gorbachev's radical reform dating since 1985 and called *perestroika* as aforementioned, in fact, was addressed to party leaders of policy systems of SSRs, rather than to the Societies.

His major criticism (06.1987–28.06.–01.07.1988) has been toward social inertia and conservatism of Societies causing for even „*criminal activities*“ of the domestic party leaders of SSRs. He identified „*bureaucracy and corruption*“ as major problems of the Union^[1]. The Gorbachev's radical reform affects all SSRs' party leaders and ministers. He has regarded his proposal as further step in development of the socialist democracy of RSFSR. It was designed in 1986 chiefly as *electoral legal reform*. Due to his reform, Gorbachev lost majority of party leaders of SSRs. The issue of electoral legal reform was never been directly raised in 1986. Instead of, in 01.1987 the final agreement that has been met by SSRs was that the electoral reform is under the SSRs parties' own rules.

Even, when Gorbachev has tried to affect on party leaders of SSRs; for instance, *via* blockade as in the case of Lithuanian (1990), he was forced to retreat on this blockade. In the latter case, this has been done by Yeltsin, who already has been elected as post of President of RSFSR. However, the blockade was attempt to prevent the corruption practice of party leaders in the latter SSR. At this point, I would like to note that, perhaps, some readers could worry that my account for the facts from that time seems to leave out of an objective view.

However, among the former SSRs the International Crime Victims Survey show at about 21% of the officers of state in SSRs within 1991-1992^[2]. Even higher value (23%) is accounted for Vilnius (2000)^[3]. The interested reader might be aware that the latter statement means an attack on a rather revanchist (anti-Russian) policy of some post-SSRs including some other also Eastern European States, however, the percentage of businesses victimised by fraud by employees, for example, in 1999 in the Capitals of Bulgaria, Lithuania, Ukraine, and Russia show the following quantities: Sofia (10%), Vilnius (11%), Kiev (13%), and Moscow (10%) (p.147^[6]). Remarkably, there are comparable values accounting for the difference in number of population of these Capitals ranging from at about 2 million people in Sofia to at about 9 million people in Moscow-oblast. There is unable to accept indifferently a claim of higher percentage corruption cases among officers of state of the small Eastern European States including post-SSRs ones, rather than in Russia in 1980s-1990s.

The preceding remarks on the major purpose of Gorbachev's radical legal reform (1985-1990) aim at disqualifying the mostly preferred position of post-SSRs policy elites of a lack of self-responsibility for events of the discussed period. These last remarks on indicate that domestic party leaders of SSRs bear responsibility for development of Republics, during that time.

To understand in-depth what there were the circumstances at that time, there can be considered additional arguments. For instance, the fact, that there was electoral legal reform (01.12.1988), which has been object of public discussion, as well. However, the suggested issue of measures which should be reformed in order to guarantee the independence of judges according to the strictly democracy principle of the rule of law has neither be completed nor accepted on 28.11.1988.

There were 300000 specific comments on the reformed law and an extended discussion, which has been performed, namely due to Estonian Popular Front's position and, generally, the Baltic States' ones that the Gorbachev's reform of the law was rather prejudicial to the rights of their SSRs and minority nationalities, therein.

I should include to argue further against Mr. Meri's statements highlighting that in 1988 Gorbachev has proposed a change of Article 119(13) allowing the Supreme Soviet Presidium to declare the so-called '*military or emergency situation*', which has been criticized by the Baltics SSRs together with text of Article 113(7) regarding „*regulatory power*“ given to RSFSR Supreme Soviet, which are classified as „*too extensives*“ by Estonians; thus, highlighting the political overtones in the jurisprudence of independent SSRs, during that time. The preparatory group of the Estonian Supreme Soviet refuse to accept these Gorbachev's suggestions. The explicit remark on was that the legislation should be agreed not by a majority, but by each SSRs, separately. Due to complete independence of Estonia the Gorbachev's reform has been accepted as centralizing in character. The statistic above, however, rather indicates that their evaluation of the Gorbachev's reform is an attempt to gain a complete independence of the legal authorities including the own ones with, thus, suggested increasing in measures of independence of judges. Therefore, obviously the statements by Mr. Meri, regarding „*...loss of Estonia's independence...*“ (above) over period 1953-1991 disagree the facts of both the Estonian and Russia new histories.

Useful references to author's note (2)

[1] BBC Monitoring, Former Soviet Union, 29 June (2009), cited in *Johnson's Russia List*, no. 121, 1 July (2009), item 5.

[2] A. Siemaszko, 'Central and Eastern European victimisation rates: to compare or not to compare?': In A. del Frate et al. (eds.), *Understanding crime: experiences of crime and crime control* (Rome: UNICRI, 1993), p.92.

[3] A. del Frate, J. van Kesteren, *Criminal victimisation in urban Europe: key findings of the 2000 International Crime Victim Surveys* (Turin: UNICRI, 2004), pp.25–28

[4] C. Cosman, *Conflict in the Soviet Union*. Human Rights Watch (1990) [https://www.hrw.org/reports/KAZAK90O.pdf].

[5] B. Brown, *Kazakhstan: The Alma-Ata Events of 1986 Reexamined*. Report on the USSR. 2 (1990) 25–27.

[6] A. del Frate, *The international crime business survey: Findings from nine Central–Eastern European Cities*, *European Journal on Criminal Policy and Research* 10 (2004) 137–161.

Because all of acts/events during the discussed period; and, particularly within 1985-1990 one, which is accepted as crucial period of RSFSR's dissolution had/have their own mainly ethno-national origin, and have latter come together with Alma-Ata Treaty (21.12.1991) signed by Governments of eleven States from post-SSRs, it might be useful to mention an event also showing the level of independence of SSRs and also impacting crucially on RSFSR's stability. The highlights are on Armenia SSR. Within 1987-1988 Armenian nationalists organized movement requesting return of Nagorno-Karabakh Autonomous Oblast. (Armenian earthquake on 07.12.1988 see preceding slides.) It is neighboring oblast populated with ethnic Armenians closed to Azerbaijan^[1]. The movement activity has been regarded as nutshell of latter full-scale armed conflict between Armenian and Azerbaijani SSRs. The Gorbachev's statement was that an intention of transferring area to Armenia would "*provoke genocide.*" The Soviet authorities sent security forces to the region (02.1988), in fact, when Azeris in Sumgait (a town near Baku) have committed grisly attacks on ethnic Armenians.

Such social processes are observed in all type socio-policy systems including in conditions of democracy; also, many of them are social-phenomena of modern histories of States of both the Eastern and Western Europe. In the case above, despite, it aimed at preventing genocide of ethnic minority group Armenians in Azerbaijan the socio-policy system of RSFSR is classified as inconsistent in use of *repression* and *accommodation*^[2,3]. The ethnic conflict Armenia SSR-Azerbaijan SSR is out of the scope of this contribution. I should only connect with Mr. Meri's statement about level of *independence of state* of SSRs within RSFSR and major affect of policy-decisions of particular Republics such as Estonia and Armenia significantly contributing to the dissolution process of RSFSR. The author's statement is that they crucially destabilized the Gorbachev's administration.

The fact that, there is a lack of use of force in SSRs is regarded as inciting corresponding ethnic group-peoples to support and even take part in domestic nationalist movements^[2,3]. Even, there is claimed that used of external force in a conflict has a rather stimulated effect than a repressed one^[4].

In 1985-1989 the used even limited scale force by RSFSR in ethnic unrests between Armenian SSR and Azerbaijan SSR, perhaps, contributes as destabilizing factor (*iv*) together with the aforementioned (*i*)–(*iii*) ones.

There are controversy statements regarding affect of use of external force on ethnic challenges, generally. Authors' perspectives frequently vary considerably. The fact that ethnic Russians account for *ca.* 50% of RSFSR population within 1945-1991 of a multi-ethics Soviet Union and there is loosened control over domestic policy elites of SSRs have resulted to new atmosphere to pursue own SSRs agendas which can be addressed to cause for many ethnic unrests, during that time, which are well-documented. It is important, however, to distinguish between these ethnic unrests among former SSRs of RSFSR and the present-day Ukraine-Russian conflict in the context of the victimology.

However, to the present-day ethnic Russian victims due to Ukraine-Russia conflict (2014-(2024)) together with victim State Russia, there should be added the Russian victims due to Chernobyl act in Ukraine SSR together with victim state RSFSR within 1986-1991 and State Russia 1991-present.

(Ethnic Belarusians and State Belarus victims, including, Belarus SSR due to Ukraine-Russia conflict (2014-(2024)) and Chernobyl act in Ukraine SSR are out of scope of this contribution.)

From perspective of events from 1989-1990 and issue of how ethnic group peoples behave mutually and change themselves, looking at socio-policy structures of Unions or Federations it could be said that due to facts shown above Russia were rather unable to be ethnic factor or actor in these ethnic unrests^[5] or environmental nationalist movements within SSRs.

Due to factors (*i*)–(*iii*) sketched on preceding slides Gorbachev has never been looked at establishing Russia as center of authority *via* forced intervention in the above mentioned ethnic unrests^[5] or protests within SSRs, which is speculation when describing Gorbachev's administration policy decisions within 1986-1991. The author's statement is that he has recognized the victimology of Russians and RSFSR. The same is valid to policy-decisions by Yeltsin's administration, and Yeltsin himself; and, the current administration of the Russian Federation, as well. In fact, Gorbachev's administration as an effort to prevent genocide has increased the risk of socio-policy system of RSFSR; thus, affecting on policy elite of both the RSFSR and SSRs.

The Gorbachev's administration policy decisions do not affect on the Society. Most Russians are described as "*shocked by the strength of the national feeling*" in SSRs (1989)^[6].

There is demonstrated solidarity with the Baltic nations including toward unofficial Lithuanian and Latvian "embassies" in Moscow (1991)^[7]. More than 150000 Russians protested in Moscow on 20.01.1991 against violent clampdown in Baltics^[8], for instance. However, these mass-protests in Russia determined the Russians' decisive vote for Boris Yeltsin in his Presidential election.

Useful references to author's note (2)

[1] E. Melander, The Nagorno-Karabakh Conflict Revisited, *Journal of Cold War Studies*. 3 (2001) 48–75.

[2] M. Lichbach, Deterrence or Escalation? The Puzzle of Aggregate Studies of Repression and Dissent. *The Journal of Conflict Resolution*. 31 (1987) 266–297.

[3] W. Moore, Repression and Dissent: Substitution, Context, and Timing. *American Journal of Political Science*. 42 (1998) 851–873.

[4] C. Brinton, *The Anatomy of Revolution*. New York: Prentice-Hall. (1952) (p.57).

[5] J. Hough, Gorbachev's Politics. *Foreign Affairs*. 68 (1989) 26–41.

[6] M. Kramer, Official Responses to Ethnic Unrest in the USSR, 1985–1991. *Russian history* 4 (2022) 289–335.

[7] K. Simonyan, Strany Baltii v gody Gorbachevskoi perestroiki. *Novaya i noveishaya istoriya* (Moscow). No. 2 (March-April 2003) pp. 44–65.

[8] Memorandum No. 8 (Top Secret) from Yuriy Prokofev, first secretary of the municipal CPSU committee in Moscow, to the CPSU Politburo and Secretariat; 22 January 1991, in Rossiiskii Gosudarstvennyi Arkhiv Noveishei Istorii (RGANI), Fond (F.) 89, Opis' (Op.) 12, Delo (D.) 31, Listy (L.) 1–2.

Republic	Dissolving date
1988	
Estonia	16.11.1988
1989	
Lithuania	18.05.1989
Latvia	28.07.1989
Azerbaijan	23.09.1989
Georgia	18.11.1989
1990	
Russia	11.06.1990
Uzbekistan	20.06.1990
Moldova	23.06.1990
Ukraine	16.07.1990
Belarus	27.07.1990
Turkmenistan	22.08.1990
Tajikistan	25.08.1990
Kazakhstan	25.10.1990
Kyrgyzstan	15.12.1990

20 % Ethic Russians become minority

Donbass				
Ethnics	1897	1926	1959	1989
Ukrainians	379000 (55.2 %)	60.0 %	64.4 %	4176000 (51.1 %)
Russians	180000	31.4 %	38.0%	3595000 (44.0 %)

In total, 26.2 % Ethic Russian minority in Ukraine

In total, 30 % Semi-Ukrainians in Ukraine

01.12.1991: Referendum for independence from USSR: 54 % „Yes“.

44 % ethnic Russian minority (Donbass)

1989 (p.264 ††) (Donetsk): 80.5 % Russian speakers

15.07.1990: Ukraine establish novel militia and security force structures.

1989 (p.267 †††) (Donbass): Donbass people stated that Russian was their 'native language.'

Ethnic Russian minority (people)

State†	Year			
	1989	2002	2011	2019
Ukraine (without Crimea and Donbass)	11360000	8330000	6500000	3800000
Belarus	1342000	1142000	785000	650000
Uzbekistan	1653000	1000000	650000	550000
Kazakhstan	6228888	4480000	3794000	3553000
Lithuania	344000	220000	175000	130000
Latvia	906000	703000	576000	487000
Estonia	475000	353000	341000	329000
Moldova	351000	220000	165000	100000

Tatarstan: 21.03.1992 (Political independence)

†S. Sushchiy, Demography Rev. (2020) 100-120.
 ††Y. Hrytsak, National Identities in Post-Soviet Ukraine: The Case of Lviv and Donetsk. Harvard Ukrainian Studies. 22 (1998) 263-281.
 †††A. Wilson, Donbas between Ukraine and Russia: The Use of History in Political Disputes. Journal of Contemporary History. 30 (1995) 265-289.

1991-1997
Russia

Ukraine

05.12.1994 (21.02.2014): Budapest Memorandum (Russia, Ukraine, The United States of America, United Kingdom)

....consult with one another with regard to commitment..."
 "...Ukraine as non-nuclear-weapon State"..."
 2. „The United States of America, the Russian Federation, and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, reaffirm their obligation to refrain from the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of Ukraine, and that none of their weapons will ever be used against Ukraine **except in self-defense or otherwise in accordance with the Charter of the United Nations**“...

03.08.1992, Yalta: Treaty of Black Sea Fleet Status of Forces

It is guided by provisions of **Paragraph 14** of the former Treaty (23.06.1992, Dagomys).

The Black Sea Fleet shall be divided between the Contracting Parties for the purpose of creating on Navy of the Russian Federation and the Navy of Ukraine.

Article 2
 Considering the interests of the Russian Federation and Ukraine as friendly States and striving to ensure security in the Black Sea basin, the Contracting Parties have decided to **establish a transition period until 1995** including until *formation* of the Navy of the Russian Federation and the Navy of Ukraine in the Black Sea. **The status of the transition period shall be determined by a separate agreement** to be concluded by the Contracting Parties before 01.10.1992.

Article 5
 The Contracting Parties have agreed that the Black Sea Fleet shall be completed for the transition period by conscripts from Russia and Ukraine in equal proportions (50 percent to 50 percent).

Article 8
 During the transition period, the Contracting Parties shall jointly use the existing infrastructure and logistics. The further development of infrastructure and logistic networks of the Russian Navy and the Ukrainian Navy shall be determined by a separate agreement.

Article 11
 Separate agreements between the Contracting Parties should specify the principles contained in this Agreement. Delegations by the States of the Contracting Parties should prepare drafts of the separated agreements by 01.10.1992.

Article 13
 By the end of the transition period, all completments of the Black Sea Fleet must be performed in accordance with Paragraph 14 of the Agreement between the Russian Federation and Ukraine on the Further Development of Interstate Relations of 23.06.1992.

Article 14
 This Agreement should be in force on its signing and should remain in force on the end of the transition period.

24.05.2014: The Lugansk People's Republic and Donetsk People's Republic have created a single State Novorossia.

08.12.1991: Belavezha Accords
 SSRs had ceased to exist as subjects of International Law and as geopolitical realities. The State called Ukrainian SSR as party to international treaties and international organizations is questionable after the shown date.

23.06.1992, Dagomys: Treaty of Black Sea Fleet Status of Forces
 (14) In connection with the creation of their Armed Forces, the Parties confirmed the importance of continuing negotiations on the creation of the Russian Navy and the Ukrainian Navy in the Black Sea on the basis of the Black Sea Fleet. They agreed to use the existing basing and logistics system on a contractual basis. Until the completion of the negotiations, the Parties agreed to refrain from unilateral actions.

15.04.1994, Moscow: Treaty of Black Sea Fleet Status of Forces
 [RUS: *Соглашении между Российской Федерацией и Украиной о поэтапном урегулировании проблем Черноморского флота*] [https://yeltsin.ru/uploads/upload/2015/06/12/rp-1994_187.pdf]

Article 2
To Ukraine is given 15% of the ships and vessels of the Black Sea Fleet; all units and parts with all the infrastructure located on the territory of Ukraine including in Crimea, as well as the infrastructure located on the territory of Donuzlav in Crimea. The rest of the Black Sea fleet and all the infrastructure...excluding the infrastructure based in Donuzlav are transferred **to the Russian Federation**,...**(or the 85 %.)**

Connected within, and in force.

28.05.1997/In force: 12.07.1999- (Reg. N 1997075†): Treaty of Black Sea Fleet Status of Forces (SOFA)

....allows Russian military to be present not only in Crimea, but also in all territory of Ukraine, including terrestrial, aquatic, and flights areas...

Article 1
 The status of the Black Sea Fleet of the Russian Federation on the **territory of Ukraine** is determined by this Treaty **and other agreements (15.04.1994, Moscow)** between the Parties associated with the development of this Agreement.

Article 2
 For the purposes of this Agreement, the following terms shall mean:
 (1)"Military formations" — units and military units of the Black Sea Fleet of the Russian Federation **stationed on the territory of Ukraine.**
 (2)"Enterprises, organizations and institutions of the Black Sea Fleet of the Russian Federation" — facilities of the Black Sea Fleet of the Russian Federation stationed **on the territory of Ukraine**, staffed with military personnel and civilians and engaged in production, economic, medical and health-improving or other similar activities in the interests of the Black Sea Fleet of the Russian Federation.
 (3)"Place of deployment" — **designated territory, water area** where military formations are stationed.
 (4)"Persons included in military formations" — military personnel of the Russian Federation serving as part of military formations, as well as those seconded to military formations from the Russian Federation.
 (5)"Family members of persons included in military formations" — spouses, children. other relatives permanently residing with these persons, as well as persons dependent on them.

Article 6
 (1) *Military formations shall carry out their activities at their locations in accordance with the legislation of the Russian Federation...*
 (3) *The state authorities of Ukraine shall respect the status of military formations*, take necessary measures agreed upon with their command to ensure the safety of personnel, protection of property rights and the safety of the property of military formations, and shall not interfere in their internal life.
 (4) The relationships of persons included in military formations and members of their families with legal entities and individuals of Ukraine outside their locations shall be regulated by the relevant agreements of the Parties and the legislation of Ukraine.

Article 7
The construction of roads, bridges, buildings and other objects at the locations of military formations shall be carried out by the Russian Party.....

Article 8
 (2) *Military formations conduct exercises and other combat and operational training activities within the boundaries of training centers, training grounds, positional areas and dispersal areas, shooting ranges and, except for restricted areas, in designated...*

Article 9
 (1) *Restricted areas for flights of aircraft of military formations in the airspace of Ukraine are determined...*

.....
 Ratified by the Federal Assembly (Federal Law (03.07. 1999 (N 124-FZ) Coll. Legisl. Russian Federation, 1999, N 27, Art. 3186.)

21.04.2010: Kharkiv Accords (Russia, Ukraine)
 It prolonges SOFA (above) until **2042+5 years extension (or 2047.)**
Russia have committed to supply Ukraine with discounted natural gas....

Connected within, and in force.

*In context separated from the Navy Forces of Soviet Russia until 1991.

11.10.1991: RSFSR novel Treaty of the Gorbachev Treaty of RSFSR (**03.12.1990/17.12.1990**).

It is signed by the Republics as Sovereign Governments: Republic of Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia (Rossia), Republic of Tajikistan, Republic of Turkmenistan, and Republic of Uzbekistan.

The States that did not sign the Treaty were Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Moldova, and **Ukraine**.

 Ukraine

12.12.1991: Minsk I Treaty

21.12.1991: Alma-Ata Treaty

(Azerbaijan Republic, Republic of Armenia, Republic of Belorus, Republic of Kazakhstan, Republic of Kyrgyzstan, Republic of Moldova, Russian Federation (RSFSR), Republic of Tajikistan, Republic of Turkmenistan, Republic of Uzbekistan, and **Ukraine**).

... establish democratic, law-governed states, the relations between which may develop on the basis of mutual recognition and respect for state sovereignty and sovereign equality, the inalienable right to self-determination, the principles of equality and noninterference in internal affairs....

....unified command of the military- strategic forces and a single control over nuclear weapons will be

 preserved ...

1991-1997
Russia

 Ukraine

1994 (Ukraine):
40% Ukrainian speaking ethnic Ukrainians,
33-34% Russian speaking ethnic Ukrainians
21 % Russian speaking ethnic Russians (p. 263, ##).

Lviv

1995 (Donbass): 63% of Donbass residents
declared that they would vote **against
independence** if a referendum were again held.
Only 16% declared that they would actually vote
in favour of independence(p. 1099 #).

National identity (1994)	[%] (p.266 ##)
Ukrainian	73.1
Russian	13.6
Soviet	7.4

National identity (1994)	[%] (p.266 ##)
Ukrainian	39.3
Russian	30.0
Soviet***	40.0

Donetsk

1994/1995 (Ukraine):
Ukraine's total industrial production decreased by 11.5 %
and production of consumer goods by 19.1%^[1].
Ukraine's foreign investment *per capita* \$12; Hungary
(\$670), Czech Republic (\$319), and Estonia (\$298)^[1].

Russia supplies 80% of Ukraine's gas^[1].

P. Pirie, National Identity and Politics in Southern and Eastern Ukraine, Europe-Asia Studies. 48 (1996) 1079-1104

Y. Hrytsak, National Identities in Post-Soviet Ukraine: The Case of Lviv and Donetsk. Harvard Ukrainian Studies. 22 (1998) 263-281

*** "Soviet", refers to social identity uniting all USSR citizens until 1991 regardless their ethnic or religious identification (p.329; N. Lebedeva et al. (Ed.) Changing Values and Identities in the Post-Communist World, Springer Verlag, 2018, Berlin.)

[1] J. Mroz, O. Pavliuk, Ukraine: Europe's Linchpin. Foreign Affairs. 75 (1996) 52-62.

2001-2007

Russia

Ukraine

Kiev

Luhansk

Donetsk

Odessa

1991: 50 % of pre-, primary and secondary schools were officially using Ukrainian.
50 % education in Russian language.

2001: 70 % of pre-, primary and secondary schools were officially using Ukrainian.
30 % education in Russian language.

2007: Year of Russian Language (30 % Ukrainians speak Russian)

2001: 17 % of pre-, primary and secondary schools were officially using Ukrainian.
83 % education in Russian language.

2001: 14 % of pre-, primary and secondary schools were officially using Ukrainian.
86 % education in Russian language.

2001: 45 % of pre-, primary and secondary schools were officially using Ukrainian.
55 % education in Russian language.
... "Russian speaking city"...

01.05.2023: The Monument of Puschkin has been destroyed.

"The government in Kiev tolerates separatist movements in practice, though they are formally outlawed. But if they were to become a real threat, the government could try to crack down. If it did, and if the easterners fought back, nationalists in the Kremlin would be under pressure to intervene on the side of their Russian-speaking brethren. For this reason a Ukrainian version of the civil wars embroiling other former Soviet republics-Georgia and Azerbaijan, for example would be much more dangerous" [The Economist, July 3, 1993, 43].

03.2007: There are collected 170500 citizens' signatures to support Russian language in Odessa.

2006: Bilingual system (Russian and Ukrainian languages): Donets'k; Luhans'k; Kherson; Yalta; Kharkiv; Sevastopol'; Mykolaiv; Kryvyi Rih; Dnipropetrovs'k, and more (p. 78; Chapter 5, [#])

1920: Bolsheviks destroy the Monument of Ekaterina II.
29.08.2007: New Monument of Ekaterina II has been placed, again.
29.12.2022: The new Monument of Ekaterina II has been destroyed, again.

Author's note (3)

In 21.12.1991 Ukraine proclaimed independence from Soviet Russia. The ethnic Ukrainians become majority ethnic group, therein, while the ethnic Russians become minority people. As is highlighted above, the ethnic map of new Ukraine-State shows significant heterogeneity. The Russian population is gradiently disposed mainly within the Eastern Ukraine, or the old province (*guberniia*) of the Russian Empire called Novorossia; thus, including Crimean peninsula as part of the old Taurida province, as well. The latter land was empty and non-developed territory during that time — the two provinces, in fact, were created and developed almost equally and parallel within the framework of the so-called *Greek Project* by Ekaterina II. Despite, the fact that the so-called *guberniia* of the Russian Empire lacks ethnographic association, for the purposes of this contribution, there should be noted that, for instance, Crimean peninsula is the only area of Ukraine-State until 2014 where ethnic Russians are majority population (below).

Furthermore, the area corresponding to the old province Novorossia shows at about 44 % ethnic Russians, as well. Despite the fact that Ukraine SSR were/are sovereign Republic of Soviet Russia (RSFSR), there is a highlighted spatial-temporal development of province/Republic Ukraine over period 1764–1991 with an almost constant splitting of Ukrainian society. Once, the latter splitting is temporal over many Centuries; and, then, it is spatially between West and East Ukraine with river Dnieper as a formal boundary.

If the reader is not yet convinced, regarding statement that the self-identity of the Ukrainian society is not only not equal in the present-day Ukraine, but also it is spatially-temporally constant over many Centuries, then, perhaps, the next facts and pro-arguments shall provide, further partial understanding of major socio-political phenomena of the Ukrainian society within period 1991-2014.

As aforementioned, a number of ethnic conflicts has increased in post IWW period [1]. The largest number of protest and rebellion quadrupled stem from minorities' grievances in Soviet Russia. However, as author's note (1) has highlighted there is nothing inconsistent among events in post-IWW Russia which have happened in many European States after IWW; furthermore, owing to the fact that the period after 1961 of development of Soviet Russia was/is characterized not only by social relationships among a large number of ethnic, cultural, national, and social groups people, but also with contrast of government policy after Stalin's demise (1953) or the so-called *Stalinism* (1927–1961). To classify, however, the discussed period as "*era of rising minorities*" (p. 43 [1]) is wrong. A sketch of history of Ancient Rus' Empire-Russian Empire-Soviet Russia shows that the largest part of ethnic groups — there are more than 200 ethnic groups people in Soviet Russia and present-day Russia — were/are already under the territorial governance of State-Russia, in spite of their socio-political systems. Rather, there is increasing in interdependence and differentiation among ethnic groups. However, it is a common social process to many European States.

Further: If there is adopted the view that important element of ethnic conflicts, amongst others, is the *status quo* of inequality of given ethnic minority group comparing with majority one of a State as a true one, as well as if it is highlighted that under „*unequal*” there is understood inequality distribution of political, economic or military power among ethnic groups of a State, then there should be emphasized the following. Despite, the fact that ethnic Ukrainians were minority group people in Ukraine SSR until 1991 there is a lack of reason to quarrel with an assumption that ethnic Ukrainians in Ukraine SSR were/are subjects of inequality as ethnic minority in Soviet Russia even if there is doubt regarding a complete independence of SSRs in Soviet Russia, highlighting, for instance the network of the military-industrial complex, which is dependent on Russia [2].

Conversely, many facts provide arguments about a statement that ethnic Ukrainians, and Ukraine SSR were/are privilege group people, respectively, Republic within 1945–1991. For instance, (i) until 1991 in Europe, Ukraine SSR held the first place in coal and steel production; the second place in grain and milk production; the third place in meat production; in addition to produce more than half of uranium ore; at about half of tanks and missiles; *et cetera* [2].

Moreover, Ukraine SSR have been the largest importer of Russian oil and natural gas (import ca. 78%) — both oil and gas were always bought at lower prices comparing with world ones, because of an equivalent payment of natural gas for at world prices, should require \$13 billion of the budget of 1993, for example [2].

In addition, the military-industrial complex of Ukraine SSR has been regarded as powerful among other SSRs; and has occupied a second place in Soviet Russia; and accounted for 18% of all military enterprises in Soviet Union.

As work [1] comprehensively discusses classification of ethnic conflicts worldwide; thus, highlighting conflicts of the new history of Russia, there is subtle difference between *conflicts of separation* and *land demarcation* one. For instance, the ethnic conflict between Ossetians-Georgians is classified as land demarcation one [3]. In the case of Ukraine-Russia conflict (2014–2024), however, there is doubt about its classification neither as *conflict of separation* nor as *land demarcation* event. A primary reason for the latter statement and doubts is the definition of land demarcation conflict, itself. It includes claim, regarding land ownership of given territory (land area) by conflicting States. The establishment of present-day Ukraine-State is connected with the Treaty dating 21.12.1991 and determining the present-day Ukraine-State within the framework of the borderlines of Soviet Ukraine SSR. Soviet Ukraine SSR, however, were established on 30.12.1922. Six months earlier (06.1922) there was published the land property Law. The Soviet State Russia or Soviet Russia were established as only owner of land on 19.02.1918 — or at about 4 years earlier (see chronology, above.)

The land of Ukraine SSR, therefore, was a State ownership of Soviet Russia. The same is true for the largest part of Ukrainian territory until 1915, which were again Russian Empire ownership within the framework of a set of decrees and Land Codes. As new State-Ukraine dating since 21.12.1991 a claim for a land ownership as area of spatial-temporal inhabitation of ethnic Ukrainian population; thus, defining them as so-called nation is obviously unjustified. A pro-argument about the latter statement follows from the discussed cases of ethnic conflicts of land demarcation type are those ones between Armenians-Azerbaijani, Ossetian-Ingush, or Ossetian-Georgians. Despite the fact that the current contribution does not treat temporal-spatial distribution of the latter ethnic group peoples, all they are well-defined spatial-temporal ethnics as inabutation, dating many Centuries before the date 19.02.1918 or 06.1922. However, the latter claim is not valid to Ukrainians who, as slides before have already highlighted, are migrants in the territory of the old Novorossia guberniia since 1833–1860; furthermore, in the largest part of this territory they are minority population until 1947. Therefore, the territory of old province Novorossia cannot be regarded as completely settled Ukrainian territory; furthermore, temporally distributed. Thus, it is hard to claim about Ukrainian national independence, involving territory of old Novorossia province. Hypothetically, it could not be associated with area having territorial autonomy, as well. The same is true for part of West Ukraine, particularly noting provinces Galicial, Bukoina, and Transcarpathia. As it already has been written, until 1915 Ukrainians were also minority ethnic group people, therein; furthermore, there is ethnic cleaning of Slavs and Jews during the IWW within the established *Reichskommissariat* Ukraine. The ethnic cleaning of Slavs (including Ukrainians during the IWW) is explicitly highlighted, above. The fact that the ethnic Ukrainian people (as minority) until 1991 is scattered and according to the common view such minority ethnic group people strives primarily for equal opportunities with the majority ethnic group people cannot be linked with the current Ukrainian-Russian conflict (2014–2024.) due to reasons sketched, above.

Thus, it should be sharply distinguished between the armed conflicts; for instance Armenians-Azerbaijani or Ossetian-Ingush ones and Ukrainian-Russian conflict (2014–2024.) In the case of Ukraine SSR during 1945–1991, there was/is neither ethnic discrimination of Ukrainian people, nor neglected Ukrainian Republic.

Therefore, in order to in-depth understand the socio-political phenomena of present-day Ukrainian society, there should be useful to concentrate on subtle differences — the difference between the aforementioned two types of conflicts has been highlighted as virtually nonexistent — thus, discussing and looking at other factors inducing frequently ethnic conflicts worldwide. For instance, these are religion, inflammatory tracts, political demagoguery, and folklore sick from history, ethnic prejudices; half-truths; and more.

Perhaps, in this case there should be highlighted effect of historical writings on political situation in some of former Republics of Soviet Russia, including Ukraine SSR who have been (are) incorporated into ethnic self-determination processes, however, lacking objective true of historical writings associated with (un)known historical (arti)facts. The affect of historical writing would be promoter of the conflicts.

In addition to possible mislead of society, due to historian (arti)facts, there should be added another one, from the history of Ukraine, which has been specifically highlighted by the author of [3], stating ...*"Few people in the West know how the Ukrainians were called under the Tsarist regime. The official term for them was "Malorossy" (Little Russians), since the Slavic part of the European Russia consisted of Great Russia (Russia proper), Little Russia (Ukraine), and White Russia (Belarus)" (p.117 [3])*.

However, the association between province "Little Russia" with present-day "Ukraine" from perspective of territory, which is broadly performed by many other authors of the so-called social sciences is wrong. The so-called guberniia "Little Russia" was, in fact, a small territory of present-day Ukraine (above). Thus, the link between old guberniia Little Russia with present-day territory of Ukraine, could be addressed to, rather factor called "folklore sick from history".

In addition, there should be underlined that crucial to growth of nationalist movements worldwide, which could be transformed into radicalized ultra-nationalist ones, even terror organizations as those movements during the IWW (see author's note (1)) could arise, due to power-hungry political (ambitious) leaders and warlords. Do Ukrainian political and military elites since 2013 follow power-hungry and ambitious plane against the rules of democracy and free self-determination of people? Rather, yes! (See, maps of Parliamentary and Presidential votes in Ukraine 2004–2012, below.)

Useful references to author's note (3)

[1] G. Mirsky, Chapter 3: On Some Aspects of Ethnic Conflicts, In *On Ruins of Empire: Ethnicity and Nationalism in the Former Soviet Union*. Westport, CT: Praeger, Contributions in Political Science. Bloomsbury Collections (1997) [ISBN: 978-0-313-30044-8].

[2] (a) *Rossiiia 24, June 9, 1993*; (b) *Nezavisimaya Gazeta April 9, 1993*.

[3] G. Mirsky, Chapter 7: Ukraine, In *On Ruins of Empire: Ethnicity and Nationalism in the Former Soviet Union*. Westport, CT: Praeger, (1997) Contributions in Political Science. Bloomsbury Collections [ISBN: 978-0-313-30044-8].

An author's remark on statement that Transnistria is in the *self-styled "Dniester republic"* (p. 50 [1]): The author of work [1] should concentrate on map showing Transnistria during 1770-1900 adapted to some slides, above. It is also associated with statement that "Russians versus Moldavians conflict in the so-called *"Dniester republic"* (p.44 [1]) or Transnistria is classified as "no *apparent feud legacy*". It is also termed as *conflict of separation*. In the latter context, there is a lack of borderline between territories called Transnistria and Moldova neither before 30.12.1922 nor within (30.12.1922)–(21.12.1991).

(See map of Bessarabia, herein: [K. Berkhoff, *Harvest of Despair: Life and Death in Ukraine under Nazi Rule*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, 2004 [ISBN 0674013131].)

2013: The events (2014) in Crimea originated from Ukrainian 'European movement' protests 2013-2014 regarding Ukrainian cooperation with European Union. (Euro-Maidan protest in Kiev, 23.02.2014 (21.11.2014?)) The Ukrainian president (V(W). Ynnukov(w)ytsh) prevented them. They turned into a pro-Russia movement in Crimea requesting a returning of Autonomous Republic Crimea as part of Russian Federation, due to majority[#] ethnic Russians in Crimea and their requested rights for self-determination. The pro-Russia movements, in fact, in Ukraine, dated back 2013 and show increasing in activity (see next slide.)

01.03.2014 (15.48h): Russian Council authorized the use of armed forces in Crimea.

Russian Federation Constitution (12.12.1993/01.07.2020)
Article 77
 (2) *Within the limits of the jurisdiction and powers of the Russian Federation on issues under the joint jurisdiction of the Russian Federation and the constituent entities of the Russian Federation federal executive government bodies and executive government bodies of the constituent entities of the Russian Federation shall form a unified system of executive authority in the Russian Federation.*

11.03.2014: Crimean declaration of independence of Ukraine.

16.03.2014: Crimean Referendum to point Russian Federation. There are 2 questions, highlighting 2 alternatives:
 (1) ...returning of Autonomous Republic Crimea as part of Russian Federation...
 (2)...restoration of Crimean statute as part of Ukraine...

Crimea: 80.42 % people (1274096) voting (96.77 % - „Yes“ of question (1) (1233002 people).)
 Sevastopol': 85.56 % people voting (95.6 % - „Yes“ of question (1).)

17.03.2014: Crimea become part of the Russian Federation.

27.03.2014: Recognition of Republic Crimea as part of Russian Federation (Resolution: A/RES/68/262.)

19.02.1954: Presidium Supreme Council's decision of linking administratively Crimea oblast (province) to Ukraine SSR. Before, this date Crimea ar enot included in any project of the Ukraine nation.
26.04.1954: Transfer of Crimea oblast to Ukraine SSR.

1978 (Ukraine SSR Constitution)
 Crimea (autonomous statute)

1991 (Ukrainian State)
 Crimea: Autonomous statute - it is recognized.

Crimean peninsula belongs to:
Russian Empire/Russian Federation (present-day State Russia):
 21.07.1774-26.04.1954 (180 years)
 27.03.2014-present
Crimean peninsula is administratively linked to:
Ukraine SSR
 (legislative territory within 30.12.1922-08.12.1991):
 26.04.1954-08.12.1991 (37 years).

1996 (Ukraine Constitution)
Article 138
 (2) [Crimea rights]...organizing and conducting local referendums...
 (3) [Crimea rights]...managing properties that belong to Autonomous Republic Crimea“...

1998 (Constitution of Autonomous Republic Crimea)

18.05.1944 (8:00 P.M. GOKO No. 5859): Lavrentij Berija ordered all Crimean Tatars (180014 people who represented ethnic minority of 19 % of Crimean population before IWW## (p.189)) to be deported to Ural and Uzbekistan.
20.05.1944: Lavrentij Berija passed information onto Stalin that all Tatars*** were deported. In fact, all population were deported, despite, their ethnic groups; for instance, 12075 were ethnic Bulgarians.
 Crimean peninsula was empty of population on 20.05.1944.
 The motivation behind the deportation was their serving the Nazi-regime during Crimea occupation by Nazi-State 1941-1943.
 Circa 5 % (7885 people: 1481 men; 3329 women; and 4367 children) died during the deportation.
26.05.1945: Data passed onto Stalin about number of surviving people: 131 690 (36 415 families) or 165515 according to a second statistics.

24.03.2014: In Crimea, Ukraine State's blockade of the North Crimean Canal plunged Crimea into chronic water shortage; thus: What criminal responsibilities should be envisaged for Ukraine State, due to their continuous attack and damaging of water facilities of Crimea?

1948: A city with Russian Republican subordination out of Crimea[‡].
17.03.2014: Statut of Federal city.

[#]A. Charron, Whose is Crimea? Contested Sovereignty and Regional Identity. Region 5 (2016) 225-256: "...Crimea — the only region of Ukraine with an ethnic Russian majority" (p.226).
^{##}A. Osipov, Territorial Autonomy as a Tool of Minority Accommodation in the Post-Soviet Space: The Cases of Ukraine and Moldova. Studies in Ethnicity and Nationalism. 19 (2019) 187-206.
[‡]Regarding ethnicity of Crimea Tatars — see, above.
[‡]Za6RV 75 (2015) 167-194.

26.12.2004: Presidential Election Ukraine

26.03.2006: Parliamentary Election Ukraine

There is clear and sharp socio-political bipolarity of the Ukrainian society. Due to historical reasons, the self-identity of the Ukrainian society is not only not equal in the present-day Ukraine, but also it is spatially-temporally constant over many Centuries.

07.02.2010: Presidential Election Ukraine

28.10.2012: Parliamentary Election Ukraine

The abbreviation EU denotes European Union. The abbreviation RF denotes Russian Federation. The term "Federation" refers to a composite state superimposed on *de jure* equal partners – member states of the federation (G. Mirsky, Chapter 3: On Some Aspects of Ethnic Conflicts, In On Ruins of Empire: Ethnicity and Nationalism in the Former Soviet Union (1997) [ISBN: 978-0-313-30044-8], p.58.)

Belarus

2014
Russia

Kursk

2024

2014

2014

Ukraine

2014

Returned to Russia
lands

Mariupol

Odessa

Major Ukrainian military forces armed attacks against 44 % ethnic Russian minority by date (Donbass)

02.05.2014: Street deaths of dozens pro-Russian activists in Odessa. In total, 42 perished by fire in Odessa's Trade-Union Building; 6 lost their lives in earlier clashes; and 208-wounded.

09.05.2014: 14 tanks fire administrative buildings in Mariupol.

12.06.2024: 51th, 72th, 24th, and 28th mechanized brigades; also, 79th airmobile brigades of Ukrainian army start establishment of control of border, using heavy weapons (tanks, artillery, aviation, and more.)

05.05.2014: Ukrainian armed forces re-established control over towns in Donetsk and Luhansk Republics.

15.07.2014: 80th airmobile brigade, 24th brigade, battalion 'Aidar', 1st tank brigade of Ukrainian armed forces started fighting on communication linking Luhansk with Russian border. Heavy armed (Ukrainian) battalions and border guard units reinforced ca. 3000 fighters at about 150 km from Amvrosiivka and Izvaryne (Izvaryne is Donetsk checkpoint with Russia.)

12.08.2014: Same Ukrainian military forces captured Vuhlehirsk near Debaltseve, put pressure on Horlivka garrison, captured Khriashchuvate (ca. 30 km from Russia's border) and Novosvitlivka, respectively.

12-13.08.2014: Russian Federation provide military support for Donetsk and Lugansk Republics for self-determining of ethnic Russians, therein.

06.08.2024 (5.30h): Ukrainian military forces armed attack against sovereign and independent State Russia

In January, 2014, when there has been asked in Ukraine: **How the people would vote on a referendum on whether Ukraine should join European Union**, then, there have been obtained:

39.7 % of all Ukrainians would vote „yes“;

35.1 % of all Ukrainians would vote „no.“

In January, 2014, when there has been asked in Ukraine: **How the people would vote on a referendum on whether Ukraine should join Customs Union with Russia, Belarus, and Kazakhstan**, then, there have been obtained:

40.8 % of all Ukrainians would vote „yes“;

33.1 % of all Ukrainians would vote „no.“

In January, 2014, when there has been asked in Donetsk: **How the people would vote on a referendum on whether Ukraine should join Customs Union with Russia, Belarus, and Kazakhstan**, then, there have been obtained:

64.5 % of all Ukrainians would vote „yes“;

10.9 % of all Ukrainians would vote „no.“

Donbass in 2014 (before date 12-13.08.2014)

Crimes committed by Ukrainian military armed forces :

Statistics: At least 10090 people (2777 civilians) have been killed; and at least 23966 injured.

Other statistics: At least 13000 people (3300 civilians) have been killed and 1.6 million people displaced.

Stage III. Dehumanization of the Victim*

Key questions: How were victims dehumanized? Is dehumanization of victims universal in genocides?

8. Did the perpetrator attempt to blame its problems on the victim group? If so, how?

Yes...under updating.

9. Was the victim group negatively labeled?

Yes.

a. What labels were used?

Ethnic Russians are labeled as “Untermenschen” (a Nazi-slogan.)

(From Nazi perspective, Slavs were racially inferior and the IIWW was regarded as „war of extermination“. The racism was the motor behind destroying most of the Russians during IIWW.

b. Were any of the labels based on the victim group's ethnicity, race, religion, language, or other attributes?

Yes: See, point 6 (Stage II), above (not published, herein.)

c. Did any of the labels imply that the victims were a source of pollution to the perpetrator group or state? (note especially labels that implied a need for eugenic measures or ethnic cleansing of a territory or population)

During 2014-2024 at least 53 % of the ethnic Russians from Donbass have been displaced; In 2014 at least 0.45 % of civilian ethnic Russians from Donbass have been killed.